

Mechanism of staphylococcal resistance to clinically relevant antibiotics

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ABSTRACT

Staphylococcus aureus, a notorious pathogen with versatile virulence, poses a significant challenge to current antibiotic treatments due to its ability to develop resistance mechanisms against a variety of clinically relevant antibiotics. In this comprehensive review, we carefully dissect the resistance mechanisms employed by *S. aureus* against various antibiotics commonly used in clinical settings. The article navigates through intricate molecular pathways, elucidating the mechanisms by which *S. aureus* evades the therapeutic efficacy of antibiotics, such as β -lactams, vancomycin, daptomycin, linezolid, etc. Each antibiotic is scrutinised for its mechanism of action, impact on bacterial physiology, and the corresponding resistance strategies adopted by *S. aureus*. By synthesising the knowledge surrounding these resistance mechanisms, this review aims to serve as a comprehensive resource that provides a foundation for the development of innovative therapeutic strategies and alternative treatments for *S. aureus* infections. Understanding the evolving landscape of antibiotic resistance is imperative for devising effective countermeasures in the battle against this formidable pathogen.

1. Introduction

Bacteria possess remarkable genetic flexibility, enabling them to adapt to diverse environmental challenges effectively (Munita and Arias, 2016). This confers them the ability to use antibacterial agents to increase their competitiveness in communities of microorganisms in the environment, but it also lets them to develop mechanisms preventing the toxic effects of medically employed antimicrobials. These substances, commonly referred to as antibiotics, have found wide application not only in human medicine, but also in agriculture, especially in plant and animal production (Lai et al., 2022). This has caused a significant increase in their concentration in the environment, which, together with their often-inappropriate prescription and use, has resulted in tremendous selection pressure promoting their antibiotic resistance (AR) (Davies and Davies, 2010). Therefore, 70 years after the antibiotics' discovery, we are currently entering a post-antibiotic era when the effective treatment for bacterial infections will no longer be available. In the European Union, infections AR bacteria cause 33,000 deaths and 2.5 million extra days of hospitalization annually (Ratia et al., 2022). In particular, multidrug resistant (MDR) bacteria, which are resistant to three or more classes of antibiotics, and pan-resistant bacteria, which are resistant to all available antibiotics, are a serious problem. Infections caused by such pathogens increase mortality, prolong treatment and

have a major impact on the economy.

Staphylococcus aureus is an opportunistic Gram-positive bacterium commonly associated with the problem of multidrug resistance. Staphylococci are often found on the skin or mucous membranes of healthy individuals without causing any problems. They are non-sporulating, non-mobile, catalase-positive, facultatively anaerobic cocci. However, if the human organism becomes weakened, they can cause a variety of infectious diseases. Among staphylococci, *S. aureus* is the most invasive species (Jensen and Lyon, 2009). It causes acute and chronic infectious diseases (ulcers, deep tissue abscesses, endocarditis, pneumonia, etc.) that can result in life-threatening organ failure. Some of its strains are highly virulent and possess remarkable genetic plasticity that makes them able to adapt to any antimicrobial attack (Mlynarczyk-Bonikowska et al., 2022).

In the pre-antibiotic era, the prognosis of these infections was very poor and so the discovery of penicillin by Alexander Fleming in 1928 and its subsequent administration to the first patients in 1941 dramatically reversed the situation (Gaynes, 2017); but not for long. As early as in 1942, penicillin-resistant strains of *S. aureus* began to be reported (Rammelkamp and Maxon, 1942), the mechanism of resistance being the expression of β -lactamase/penicillinase, destructase cleaving the β -lactam ring of penicillin. In response to the emergence and spread of penicillin resistance, semisynthetic methicillin (Peacock and Paterson,

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2015) was developed. Methicillin is a substituted β -lactam ring structurally similar to penicillin; however, it is resistant to the action of penicillinase. It was introduced to the market in 1959, but also in this case, only two years later, the first methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) strains were isolated (Barber, 1961). During the 1970s and 1980s, methicillin and cephalosporins were massively used in hospitals, dramatically increasing the incidence of MRSA infections (Mlynarczyk-Bonikowska et al., 2022). Because of its high frequency as a nosocomial infection, it began to be referred to as HA-MRSA (from hospital-acquired MRSA). Later, some authors started to use the extended designation HCA-MRSA (from health care-associated MRSA) to reflect the capture of these infections in any health care facility (Bishara et al., 2012). During the 1990s, MRSA infections have begun to occur even among young people without risk factors. Due to significant differences in epidemiology and genetic characteristics such as virulence factors and antibiotic resistance profile, community-acquired infections began to be referred to as CA-MRSA (from community-associated MRSA). CA-MRSA strains lack the MDR phenotype (Lawrence, 2022), are usually characterized by β -lactam resistance, and also by the presence of specific virulence factors (Tsuji et al., 2007) such as Panton-Valentine leukocidin (PVL), which is associated with a higher risk of skin and soft tissue infections and has a strong epidemiological association with CA-MRSA strains (David and Daum, 2010). In contrast, HA-MRSA strains often have a different set of virulence factors (PVL detection is rare) and also carry multiple resistance mechanisms to other antibiotic classes (David and Daum, 2010). These strains are more likely to cause severe invasive infections.

Concerns about MRSA infections persist today. Although so-called anti-MRSA cephalosporins were approved in the EU after 2010 (Newman et al., 2015), strains resistant to these antibiotics have also been reported. In the last decade, MRSA infection rates have increased globally and have reached epidemic levels in many parts of the world (Kumar et al., 2020). Their clinical treatment has become very difficult and represents a significant therapeutic challenge (Guo et al., 2020). This is also why *S. aureus* has been categorized as a high priority for the discovery and development of new antibiotics by the World Health Organization (Anon, 2017).

Much evidence has already demonstrated that the resistance mechanisms of *S. aureus* are very complex (Guo et al., 2020). The characterisation of these genes and the early understanding and elucidation of AR mechanisms at the molecular level is extremely important for maintaining the effectiveness of antibiotics and for designing new strategies to limit not only the spread but also the emergence of resistance. Thus, research into the nature of genes encoding antibiotic resistance has been an important area of study in recent years. This review follows up on reviews of Mlynarczyk et al (Mlynarczyk-Bonikowska et al., 2022), and Lade et al (Lade et al., 2022), published in 2022. In comparison, our review incorporates the latest research findings and advances in the field, providing readers with the most up-to-date information available. In addition, we offer a more comprehensive analysis by examining individual antibiotics, including both traditional and emerging ones, and their mechanisms of action, as well as examining a broader spectrum of resistance mechanisms and their effects. Finally, our review may provide unique insights or perspectives not covered in earlier publications and offer readers new perspectives on a given topic.

2. Genetic basis of antibiotic resistance

Antibiotics are divided into four basic groups according to their mechanism of action: (i) inhibition of cell wall synthesis, (ii) disruption of cytoplasmic membrane function, (iii) inhibition of nucleic acids replication/transcription, and (iv) inhibition of proteosynthesis. Despite this chemical and target heterogeneity, however, bacteria have evolved sophisticated mechanisms that provide them with a resistant phenotype.

2.1. Definition of antibiotic resistance

There are two leading scientific organisations that provide standards, recommendations and guidelines for antibiotic resistance testing (Kahlmeter et al., 2019). While the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) is predominant in the United States, the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) is preferred in Europe. Their aim is to harmonise methods for antimicrobial susceptibility testing and to ensure the quality of the results, which is very important for selecting appropriate treatment for infections caused by resistant bacteria.

According to EUCAST, so-called breakpoint concentrations, which are selected clinical values that define whether bacteria are sensitive or resistant to each clinically relevant antibiotic, serve as criteria for interpreting antibiotic resistance (EUCAST Clinical Breakpoint Tables, 2024). A bacterial strain whose minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) is greater than the breakpoint value can be defined as resistant.

2.2. Types of resistance

There are several types of antibiotic resistance occurring in bacteria. So-called intrinsic resistance is a natural property of some bacteria that makes them resistant to certain antibiotics. It is manifested, for example, by the inability of the antibiotic molecule to penetrate the cell wall/membrane and reach its target. Another type is so-called adaptive resistance, in which gene expression is altered due to the presence of antimicrobial agents (Costa and Machado, 2017). However, such resistance is transient, non-hereditary and reversion of the resistant phenotype can be achieved by simply removing the inducer (Costa and Machado, 2017). In the context of the worldwide spread of AR, bacteria with intrinsic or adaptive resistance are not considered a threat (Fernández et al., 2011). A very alarming problem is the so-called acquired resistance. It refers to the ability of bacteria to develop, through genetic changes, resistance to antibiotics to which they were previously sensitive. This can occur as a result of spontaneous mutations in chromosomal genes or, more commonly, by acquisition of resistant genes through horizontal gene transfer (HGT) (Gallo and Puglia, 2013). During HGT, mobile genetic elements such as plasmids, transposons, integrons or chromosomal gene cassettes are transferred. It is now evident that HGT is the driving force behind the evolution of antibiotic (multi) resistance (Jensen and Lyon, 2009). HGT can occur by one of three mechanisms: (i) conjugation, in which contact between two cells is mediated *via* pilus, (ii) transduction, in which the transfer of genetic information is ensured by bacteriophages, and (iii) transformation, which consists in the uptake of foreign DNA (linear or on a plasmid) from the environment where it has been released, e.g., after cell lysis. The spread of AR in a hospital setting often involves conjugation. It also occurs to a large extent in the gastrointestinal tract of patients under antibiotic treatment (Munita and Arias, 2016).

2.3. Mechanisms of resistance

Five antibiotic resistance mechanisms are currently known (Fig. 1). The first one is the inactivation of the antibiotic by its degradation or modification. It is used both by Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria. Examples include inactivation of aminoglycosides by the action of aminoglycoside modifying enzymes (nucleotidyltransferase, phosphotransferase or acetyltransferase (Ramirez and Tolmashy, 2010a)), or enzymatic destruction of β -lactam antibiotics by β -lactamases. The second and third mechanisms decrease the intracellular concentration of antibiotics. The second mechanism is oriented on antibiotics, such as β -lactams, tetracyclines or some fluoroquinolones, which require transport across the outer membrane of Gram-negative bacteria to reach their target. However, the bacterium can modify its structure and thus reduce the permeability to these molecules. The third resistance mechanism is based on the fact, that antibiotics can also be transported from the

Fig. 1. Mechanism of bacterial antibiotic resistance. Met – methylated.

cytoplasm to the extracellular fluid by so-called active efflux, which uses tripartite efflux pumps (e.g., fluoroquinolones in *S. aureus*). The fourth mechanism involves the target-based resistance. It can be acquired by mutations in the genes encoding such a target, by enzymatic modification of the antibiotic-binding site, or by protection of the drug target (Munita and Arias, 2016). One well-characterized example of the first case is resistance to fluoroquinolones, which inhibit two key enzymes of DNA replication, topoisomerase IV and DNA gyrase. However, chromosomal mutations can alter the structure of these enzymes targeted by fluoroquinolones and make them less sensitive to inhibition. In contrast, the *erm* genes are an example of enzymatic binding site conversion; they encode ribosomal methyltransferases that confer resistance to macrolides by methylating the active site of the ribosome. The last case is represented, for example, by ribosomal protection proteins (RPPs) or Fus proteins. RPPs play a key role in protecting bacterial ribosomes from the inhibitory effects of specific antibiotics. The mechanism of action involves direct interaction of RPP with the ribosome at a site overlapping the antibiotic binding site, which prevents binding of the antibiotic and inhibits protein synthesis. RPPs can be divided into two classes: Tet proteins causing tetracycline resistance and ABC-F proteins causing multiresistance (active against, e.g., macrolides, lincosamides, oxazolidinones, phenicols, etc.). Fus proteins are key players in the resistance mechanism to fusidic acid. Fus proteins counteract inhibition of elongation factor G (EF-G) by fusidic acid by displacing this antibiotic from EF-G. The fifth mechanism of resistance consists in modification or development of an alternative pathway completely replacing the original one (bypass). Through this process, bacteria can replace the target site with a new one that exhibits the same biochemical properties but is not inhibited by the antibiotic. A well-known example is methicillin resistance in *S. aureus*, which arises due to the acquisition of a modified penicillin-binding protein (PBP2a), or vancomycin resistance in enterococci, which arises due to the acquisition of a cluster of *van* genes whose products are responsible for the substitution of D-alanyl-alanine for D-alanyl-D-lactate in the peptidoglycan structure of the cell wall.

3. Mechanisms of *S. aureus* resistance

In the following chapters, the mechanism of action of each antibiotic class will be briefly reviewed, and the mechanisms of *S. aureus* resistance will be discussed. A detailed description of the mechanism of action of antibiotics is provided in source publications or other reviews devoted to this issue (e.g., (Douglas and Laabei, 2023); Chen et al., 2023). Because of the extent of resistance caused by efflux pumps, this will be summarised in a separate chapter.

3.1. β -lactam antibiotics

The β -lactam antibiotics prevent bacterial cell wall synthesis by binding to and inhibiting enzymes called penicillin-binding proteins (PBPs), which are responsible for cross-linking peptidoglycan, the main structural component of the bacterial cell wall. Without these bonds, the cell wall loses its strength and integrity, leading to the death of the bacteria. Methicillin-sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA) strains express four different PBPs that function as transpeptidases, carboxylases, or transglycosylases (Chen et al., 2023; Navratna et al., 2010). PBP1 (transpeptidase) plays a key role in cell growth and division. PBP2 is unique bifunctional PBP that catalyses not only transpeptidation, but also transglycosylation reaction (Berti et al., 2013). Its inhibition leads to limited peptidoglycan elongation, leakage of cytoplasmic contents and cell lysis (Navratna et al., 2010). The specific role of PBP3 (transpeptidase) remains unclear. Apart from its effect on autolysis rate, no obvious phenotype associated with its inactivation has been discovered (Pinho et al., 2000). The final group of PBP proteins is PBP4 (transpeptidase, carboxylase), which is responsible for secondary peptidoglycan cross-linking (Henze and Berger-Bächi, 1995). Genetic deletion or inhibition of these enzymes indicate that only PBP1 and PBP2 are required for normal growth of *S. aureus* (Fisher and Mobashery, 2016). The role of PBPs is to cross-link the two peptidoglycan units, which in transpeptidases occurs via a pentaglycine bridge, while in transglycosylases it occurs via sugar units (da Costa et al., 2018). Even both activities are very important for proper synthesis of the cell wall, the

transpeptidase activity is responsible for its rigidity and enhanced crosslinking (da Costa et al., 2018). The transpeptidase activity of PBPs is then specifically inhibited by β -lactam antibiotics (Ferrer-González et al., 2017).

3.1.1. Penicillin resistance

Penicillin resistance arises from the acquisition of the ability to produce β -lactamase/penicillinase, which hydrolyses the β -lactam ring. The resulting open-ring β -lactams cannot bind to PBPs and lose their bactericidal effect. Penicillinase is encoded by the *blaZ* gene carried by transposons localized on plasmids or integrated into the bacterial chromosome (Foster, 2017) and after expression, it is released into the extracellular environment, where it prevents antibiotics from reaching their targets in the cell (Anon, 2017; Foster, 2017).

Penicillinase synthesis is inducible and occurs only when the *Staphylococcus* is exposed to β -lactams. Expression of the *blaZ* gene is controlled by the two-component *blaR1-blaI* regulatory system, the products of which are the BlaR1 (antirepressor) and BlaI (repressor) proteins (Lowy, 2003). The transmembrane sensor and signal transducer BlaR1 detects the presence of β -lactams in the extracellular environment through its penicillin-binding domain (PBD) (Peacock and Paterson, 2015). The β -lactam within the PBD binding site mediates acylation, which causes a conformational change, thereby stimulating autocatalytic cleavage of BlaR1 (Peacock and Paterson, 2015). The cleavage-activated intracellular metalloproteinase domain (MPD) then directly cleaves BlaI into inactive fragments, thereby inducing *blaZ* expression (Alexander et al., 2023). The scheme of the regulation of *blaZ* expression is shown in Fig. 2.

3.1.2. Methicillin and other β -lactam resistances

Methicillin resistance is now understood as resistance to virtually all β -lactams (Foster, 2017). It is caused by the acquisition of the *mecA* gene, which encodes a modified PBP referred to as PBP2a (Hartman and Tomasz, 1984) or PBP2' (Utsui and Yokota, 1985). Its name implies that it is a homologue of the PBP2 protein. PBP2a is characterized by low affinity for all β -lactams (except 5th generation cephalosporins), which is due to masking of the active site of the transpeptidase domain in a cleft inaccessible to antibiotics (Strynadka and Lim, 2002). Thus, PBP2a can synthesize peptidoglycan but has special requirements for cell wall precursors (Bennett et al., 2019). The provision of these substrates thus requires the functionality of several other genes. The *femA* and *femB* chromosomal genes (*fem* - Factors Essential for Methicillin resistance) are responsible for the addition of glycine residues to the side chain to form pentaglycine, which is essential for PBP2a function and cell wall formation (Zuniga et al., 2020). Disruption of *fem* genes affects *mecA* expression (Bennett et al., 2019). Another fragility of PBP2a is that it carries only transpeptidase activity and lacks the transglycosylase domain (Bennett et al., 2019). When the transpeptidase activity of PBP2 is inhibited, cooperation between PBP2a and PBP2 is required for peptidoglycan synthesis (Foster, 2017).

MecA, now considered a resistance marker for MRSA detection, is localized on mobile genetic elements called staphylococcal cassette chromosome *mec* (SCCmec), which are present only in MRSA strains (Uddin and Ahn, 2017). In addition to *mecA*, SCCmec elements also encode *ccr* (chromosome cassette recombinase) genes, which mediate SCCmec excision and integration (Jensen and Lyon, 2009), and *mecR1-mecI*. The latter two genes encode the regulatory proteins MecR1 and MecI, which are homologous to the BlaR1-BlaI regulatory system. The transcription of *mecA* gene is regulated similarly to that of *blaZ*.

Fig. 2. The mechanism of β -lactam resistance based on the induction of β -lactamase cleaving the β -lactam ring in the presence of penicillin.

Induction of *mecA* transcription occurs only after exposure of the bacterium to β -lactams, through a signalling cascade mediated by MecR1, resulting in removal of the DNA-binding protein MecI from the operator region and transcription of *mecA*. Some MRSA strains possess deletions or mutations in the *mecI* gene and the *mecA* promoter, resulting in constitutive expression (Rosato et al., 2003). Furthermore, the similarity of the mentioned regulatory systems has been found to allow BlaR1-BlaI to induce *mecA* expression (Lowy, 2003). Accordingly, many types of SCCmec elements lack functional MecI and/or MecR1 (Alexander et al., 2023). Thus, BlaR1 and BlaI are critically important for β -lactam resistance in MRSA (Alexander et al., 2023). Overall, *mecA* expression varies from strain to strain depending on the presence of Bla and Mec regulatory systems, Fem proteins, or various deletions and mutations in the aforementioned genes.

In 2011, a new gene named *mecC* (Paterson et al., 2013) was discovered, which shows 63 % homology with the *mecA* gene (Foster, 2017). It encodes the PBP2c protein, which confers a PBP2a-like β -lactam resistance to staphylococci. It was isolated first from farm animals, but then also from humans (Paterson et al., 2013). Although the frequency of *mecC*-MRSA has increased in recent years (Paterson et al., 2013; McClure et al., 2020), it is not part of routine diagnostic testing for MRSA in many laboratories (Lozano et al., 2020). This poses a risk of such strains being falsely labelled as MSSA, which may adversely affect treatment decisions.

3.1.3. Non-*mecA*/*mecC* methicillin resistance

In addition to the synthesis of PBP2a/PBP2c, β -lactam staphylococcal resistance may be caused by other mechanisms. Thus, some MRSA strains are associated with so-called non-*mec* resistance mechanisms. One example is strains with the BORSA (borderline oxacillin-resistant *S. aureus*) phenotype, which show low levels of resistance to oxacillin while being negative for *mec* genes. The MIC values (1–8 mg/l) of such strains are around the borderline concentration of oxacillin (>2 mg/l) (Iyer, 2022). Their resistance is typically associated with overexpression and overproduction of penicillinase (Hryniewicz and Garbacz, 2017). Some studies also suggest that penicillinase in BORSA acts as an extended-spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL) (Nomura et al., 2020). BORSA strains are rare and considered clinically irrelevant; this is evidenced by the fact that EUCAST does not recommend their screening (EUCAST Clinical Breakpoint Tables, 2024). Nevertheless, they may still pose a significant therapeutic threat (Hryniewicz and Garbacz, 2017).

A second example of a *mec*-independent form of resistance is the MODSA (*modified S. aureus*) phenotype (Gitman et al., 2021). Such isolates are characterized by modifications caused by mutations in *S. aureus* proteins. The most frequent and significant mutations leading to MODSA are in the gene itself and/or the *pbp4* promoter (Navratna et al., 2010; da Costa et al., 2018; Gitman et al., 2021; Memmi et al., 2008; Hamilton et al., 2017). However, mutations have also been described in the *pbp2* gene, *acrB* (encoding a cation efflux transporter) (Memmi et al., 2008; Hamilton et al., 2017) and in genes involved in PBP4 production such as *gdpP* (encoding a cyclic di-AMP phosphodiesterase) and *yjbH* (encoding a disulphide stress effector) (Memmi et al., 2008; Argudín et al., 2018).

PBP4 is a non-essential PBP and the only representative of low molecular weight PBPs in *S. aureus*. It is unique among low molecular weight PBPs in that it possesses two activities (transpeptidase and carboxylase) (Gitman et al., 2021). It has been found that PBP4 can confer high levels of resistance across the entire β -lactam class and is essential for β -lactam resistance in CA-MRSA strains (Memmi et al., 2008). Two types of mutations have been detected in *pbp4* mutant strains: (i) missense mutations in *pbp4* near the serine in the active site (e.g., E183A and F241R (Memmi et al., 2008)) and (ii) promoter mutations in *pbp4* (da Costa et al., 2018). While the role of missense mutations is not entirely clear (Chatterjee et al., 2017), promoter mutations lead to overexpression of PBP4 and, due to increased transpeptidase activity, also to the production of highly amplified peptidoglycan

(Memmi et al., 2008). The essential role that PBP4 plays in β -lactam resistance has also been demonstrated by deletion of *pbp4*, which completely reversed the resistant phenotype of such strains back to sensitive (da Costa et al., 2018; Gitman et al., 2021).

3.1.4. 5th generation cephalosporins resistance

Following the spread of MRSA strains, the search for compounds with affinity for MRSA-specific PBP2a, which has an active site hidden in the cleft and thus prevents access and binding of β -lactams, has been a task of intense research (Bennett et al., 2019). After 2010, 5th generation cephalosporins, ceftobiprole and ceftaroline, also referred to as anti-MRSA or MRSA-active cephalosporins with a broad spectrum of activity, were approved in the European Union (Argudín et al., 2018). Both are administered as prodrugs; ceftobiprole and ceftaroline are bioactive metabolites of ceftobiprole medocaril and ceftaroline fosamil, respectively (Bennett et al., 2019).

Ceftaroline shows excellent activity towards all PBPs (PBP1-PBP3), including PBP2a (Duplessis and Crum-Cianflone, 2011). The mechanism of action is mainly due to its pharmacophore, which is a mimetic of part of the cell wall structure (Duplessis and Crum-Cianflone, 2011). Interaction of this ethoxyimino side chain with the allosteric site of PBP2a triggers conformational changes leading to the opening of the active site where another ceftaroline molecule can bind and subsequently inhibit the whole enzyme (Duplessis and Crum-Cianflone, 2011; Acebrón et al., 2015; Greninger et al., 2016). In contrast, ceftobiprole acts through the R2 group of its structure, which binds and extends into the narrow cleft of PBP2a to reach the active site (Greninger et al., 2016; Chan et al., 2015).

The potential for the development of resistance to these new cephalosporins seemed low, but with their clinical use, reports of strains resistant to both ceftaroline and ceftobiprole began to emerge. Initially, only resistance based on mutations in *mecA* was described. The E447K substitution mutation structurally residing in the penicillin-binding domain of PBP2a appears to play a key role conferring a high level of resistance (Acebrón et al., 2015; Greninger et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2021), although several other mutations have been described in other PBP2a domains among others (Peacock and Paterson, 2015; Liu et al., 2021). Nowadays, resistance to ceftaroline and ceftobiprole is also associated with non-*mec* resistance mechanisms, especially mutations in *pbp4*, as described above (Greninger et al., 2016). Thus, it is suggested that the introduction of ceftaroline and ceftobiprole may have caused increased selection pressure for the development of MODSA strains (Peacock and Paterson, 2015).

3.2. Glycopeptide antibiotics

Glycopeptides are a group of natural and semisynthetic glycosylated peptides that exhibit bactericidal activity similar to β -lactams through inhibition of cell wall synthesis (Zeng et al., 2016). However, the exact mechanism and site of action vary. Their action is primarily achieved by binding to the dipeptide D-Ala4-D-Ala5, located at the end of a peptidoglycan precursor (GlcNac- β (1,4)-MurNAc-pentapeptide) composed of N-acetylmuramic acid (MurNAc) and N-acetylglucosamine (GlcNac) subunits. Binding of glycopeptides to this dipeptide results in the inhibition of transpeptidation and transglycosylation catalysed by PBP2 and PBP2a/c, thereby preventing further elongation and crosslinking of the peptidoglycan matrix (Foster, 2017).

The core member of this class is vancomycin, which plays an important role among antibiotics. Even today, it is still preferred in the treatment of severe infections caused by MRSA and other Gram-positive resistant pathogens. The other important antibiotic member is teicoplanin, a natural product related to vancomycin, but which carries a hydrophobic substituent and has thus been designated a lipoglycopeptide. After 2010, new semi-synthetic lipoglycopeptide derivatives were introduced, namely televancin, oritavancin and dalbavancin (Zhan et al., 2010). Their discovery was preceded by

targeted enhancement of antibacterial activity, thus in some cases their effect is exerted through additional, secondary mechanisms of action (Zeng et al., 2016).

All glycopeptides act through binding to D-Ala4-D-Ala5. Vancomycin further antagonizes peptidoglycan remodelling (Szemraj et al., 2022), thereby interfering with the autocatalytic activity of *S. aureus* (Peschel et al., 2000). The hydrophobic portion of teicoplanin acts as a membrane anchor, interacting with the lipid bilayer to enhance antibacterial activity (Beauregard et al., 1995). The mechanism of action of dalbavancin is thought to be similar to its derivative teicoplanin (Zeng et al., 2016). Oritavancin possesses a 4'-chlorobiphenylmethyl side chain that also functions as a membrane anchor providing greater stability during interaction with the dipeptide. In addition, this moiety also causes disruption of the cell membrane, resulting in membrane depolarization, permeabilization and leakage of cellular potassium ions and adenosine triphosphate (ATP) leading to cell death (Zhanet al., 2012a). The latter telavancin acts in the same way as oritavancin (Zeng et al., 2016).

3.2.1. Resistance to vancomycin and other (lipo)glycopeptides

In Gram-positive bacteria, resistance to vancomycin was very long delayed compared to antibiotics from other classes. The first isolated clinical vancomycin-resistant strain, *Enterococcus faecalis*, occurred in 1987, more than 30 years after the introduction of vancomycin into clinical practice. As a result of horizontal transfer of enterococcal resistance genes, vancomycin resistance was subsequently developed very rapidly in *S. aureus*.

Since vancomycin binds with high affinity to cell wall precursors, the mechanism of vancomycin resistance is dependent on the acquisition of a *van* group of genes encoding enzymes whose products are precursors

with lower binding activity (Zeng et al., 2016). Thus, this remodelling of peptidoglycan synthesis involves the incorporation of a modified D-Ala-D-Lac-terminated precursor and the concomitant destruction of normal D-Ala-D-Ala-terminated precursors (see Fig. 3). During the synthesis of the depsipeptide D-Ala-D-Lac, the simple hydrogen bond between the vancomycin molecule and its target is lost, reducing the antibiotic affinity for this precursor by approximately 1000× (Munita and Arias, 2016).

Glycopeptide resistance in enterococci is mediated by different *van* operons named according to the type of ligase encoded. Today, nine of them are known, namely *vanA*, *vanB*, *vanC*, *vanD*, *vanE*, *vanG*, *vanL*, *vanM* and *vanN* (Cong et al., 2019). The *vanA* gene cluster is the most common resistance phenotype in enterococci and the only mechanism detected so far in VRSA (Perichon and Courvalin, 2009). *VanA* is localized on transposons located in plasmids and confers resistance to all members of this class. It consists of 7 genes encoding three groups of proteins: (i) a two-component regulatory system for expression of resistance operons (*VanS* and *VanR*), (ii) enzymes for synthesis of novel modified precursors (*VanH* and *VanA*), (iii) proteins required for hydrolysis of normal precursors (*VanX* and *VanY*), and a protein (*VanZ*) with unknown function (Munita and Arias, 2016). It also encodes two genes, *ORF1* and *ORF2*, whose products, transposase and resolvase, are involved in transposition (Jacoby, 2019). Detection of an antibiotic by the integral histidine kinase *VanS*, triggers autophosphorylation of *VanS*, followed by the ATP-dependent transfer of phosphate to the regulator *VanR* (Thaker et al., 2015). This modified *VanR* binds to two promoters, one upstream of the *vanR* gene, the other upstream of *vanH*, and induces transcription of *vanHAXYZ*. *VanH* is a dehydrogenase that supplies D-lactate by reduction of pyruvate. D-Lac is then attached to the D-Ala molecule by the *VanA* ligase, resulting in the formation of the

Fig. 3. Mechanism of resistance to vancomycin. (1) The presence of vancomycin is detected by the integral histidine kinase *VanS*. (2) *VanS* initiates autophosphorylation and transfers the phosphate to the regulator *VanR*. (3) Phosphorylated *VanR* binds to two promoters (P_R and P_H) and induces transcription of the *vanHAXYZ* operon. (4) The expressed proteins modify the end of the peptide precursor to incorporate D-Ala-D-Lac instead of D-Ala-D-Ala, thereby preventing the binding between vancomycin and its target and thus conferring resistance to this antibiotic in the bacterium.

depsipeptide. The original D-Ala precursors are reduced by D, D-dipeptidase VanX. Membrane-bound D,D-carboxypeptidase hydrolyses the terminal D-Ala formed upon elimination by VanX. The function of the VanZ protein is still unclear, although it has been suggested that it might play a role in teicoplanin resistance (Jacoby, 2019).

Although vancomycin is frequently prescribed for the treatment of MRSA, the occurrence of VRSA strains remains rare. A few cases have been confirmed worldwide so far, mostly in the USA, where VRSA was also first isolated in 2002. The first detection of VRSA in Europe was reported only in 2013 in Portugal (Melo-Cristino et al., 2013).

3.2.2. Resistance caused by VISA/hVISA strains

Common vancomycin treatment failure occurs in infections caused by strains carrying acquired multiple chromosomal mutations that affect peptidoglycan biosynthesis during prolonged vancomycin treatment (Foster, 2017). These include vancomycin-intermediate *S. aureus* (VISA) and an intermediate in its evolution, heterogeneous VISA (hVISA). Vancomycin-sensitive *S. aureus* (VSSA) has MIC values of $2 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ or less, while for VISA they range from 4 to $8 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$, and for VRSA they are greater than $8 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ (EUCAST Clinical Breakpoint Tables, 2024). In the case of hVISA, most cells in the population have MICs $\leq 2 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ and are therefore interpreted as sensitive but isolates also contain a subpopulation of cells (1 among 10^6 cells) with MICs of $4\text{--}8 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ (EUCAST Clinical Breakpoint Tables, 2024). These subpopulations contain single mutations that are selected in the last step in the pathway to full resistance. While VRSA and VISA strains can have their MICs determined by standard methods, the detection and confirmation of hVISA requires population profile with area under the curve (PAP-AUC) analysis, which is very challenging and laborious for routine diagnostic laboratories and is usually only performed by reference laboratories.

The development of hVISA/VISA is an adaptive multifactorial response to sublethal doses of vancomycin (Jensen and Lyon, 2009). Although it represents a multistep process and depends on point mutations in several chromosomal genes, such strains nevertheless share the same phenotypic characteristics. Resistance is manifested by thickening of the cell wall, reduced cross-linking of peptidoglycan chains and reduced autolysis rate (Zeng et al., 2016). Multiple mutations have been found in genes encoding two-component systems (Hiramatsu et al., 2014), namely WalkR (sensor protein kinase/regulator), which, for example, regulates the transcription of genes involved in cell wall metabolism (Delaune et al., 2012), VraSR (vancomycin resistance associated sensor/regulator) that upregulates the expression of enzymes involved in peptidoglycan synthesis (Yin et al., 2006) and GraSR (glycopeptide resistance associated sensor/regulator) that plays an important role in resistance to cationic antimicrobial peptides, vancomycin or daptomycin (Chen et al., 2021). The accumulation of mutations in these genes causes increased cell wall thickness, which results in glycopeptides having to travel longer to reach their destination on the cell membrane surface. Furthermore, there is also reduced peptidoglycan cross-linking, which provides freer D-Ala-D-Ala ends serving as false targets. Moreover, the binding of a large vancomycin molecule to these ends on the outer layer of the cell wall prevents the penetration of other drug molecules and induces the so-called plugging phenomenon (Zeng et al., 2016). Substitution mutations in the *rpoB*, *rpoC*, *msrR*, *sle1*, *cmk* and *fdh2* genes have also been associated with the resistant hVISA/VISA phenotype (Foster, 2017; Hiramatsu et al., 2014; Zhu et al., 2021).

In-vitro mutational frequency of resistance to televancin, oritavancin and dalbavancin has been reported in a very limited way and thus they are still effective in the treatment of infections caused by MSSA, MRSA and VISA strains (Crotty et al., 2016). Since resistance to vancomycin required more than 30 years in clinical practice and the acquisition of several genes before it became prevalent, semisynthetic derivatives are expected to develop resistance even more slowly (Zeng et al., 2016). This demonstrates the unique mechanism of action of these antibiotics.

3.3. Lipopeptide antibiotics

Daptomycin is a cyclic lipopeptide antibiotic produced by the soil bacterium *Streptomyces roseosporus* approved as the first lipopeptide in clinical use by the FDA in 2003 and by the European Medical Agency in 2006 (Gonzalez-Ruiz et al., 2011; Grein et al., 2020). It is used for the treatment of severe and complicated skin and soft tissue infections caused by various Gram-positive bacteria, right-sided endocarditis, and bacteraemia caused by *S. aureus* (Heidary et al., 2018). Today, daptomycin is a very important antibiotic, mainly because of the prevalence of MDR bacteria. Like vancomycin, it was classified as a critically important antimicrobial in human medicine by the WHO in 2019 (Anon, 2019). It is recommended as the first alternative to vancomycin (Gonzalez-Ruiz et al., 2011), as it also shows activity against MRSA and VISA strains.

Daptomycin is structurally similar to cationic antimicrobial peptides that are produced by the innate immune system. The daptomycin molecule consists of a thirteen amino acid depsipeptide, ten amino acids of which form a cyclic core bearing three exocyclic amino acids attached to the amino-terminal end of the fatty acid decanoyl chain (see Fig. 4) (Gray and Wenzel, 2020). Several of the amino acids within the daptomycin core are unusual, including ornithine, kynurenine, or 3-methylglutamic acid, the latter two of which are crucial for the antibacterial activity of daptomycin (Grünewald et al., 2004).

Daptomycin achieves its bactericidal activity by interacting with the cell membrane. Since the native antibiotic molecule carries a negative charge, the presence of a physiological concentration of calcium ions is required for its effect (Gómez Casanova et al., 2017). This is because in the extracellular environment, a Ca^{2+} complex is formed with daptomycin (DAP-Ca), and calcium masks the anionic nature of daptomycin and therefore DAP-Ca behaves as a cationic peptide when interacting with the bacterial cell (Grein et al., 2020). After the formation of DAP-Ca, the complex subsequently oligomerizes to form micellar structures that penetrate the cell wall (Foster, 2017). Upon approaching the cell membrane, the micelles dissociate and Ca^{2+} ions help daptomycin to incorporate into the cytoplasmic membrane by binding to the negatively charged phospholipid phosphatidylglycerol (PG) (Gutiérrez-Chávez et al., 2021). This interaction results in aggregation of daptomycin molecules on the outer side of the membrane (Zhang et al., 2014a). Subsequently, another phospholipid, cardiolipin, also translocates these aggregates to the inner side of the membrane, resulting in pore formation (Munita and Arias, 2016; Zhang et al., 2014a). The final result of daptomycin activity is a change in the physicochemical properties of the membrane, depolarization and leakage of ions (mainly K^{+}) from the cytoplasm resulting in cell death.

3.3.1. Resistance to daptomycin

S. aureus may use several strategies to develop resistance to daptomycin. All of them result from mutations in chromosomal genes that cause alterations in cytoplasmic membrane composition (Miller et al., 2016).

The most common gene involved in increasing the positive membrane charge is *mprF* (multiple peptide resistance factor), which encodes phosphatidylglycerol lysyltransferase (Bayer et al., 2013). MprF is a bifunctional integral membrane protein whose carboxy-terminal end is responsible for the addition of a positively charged lysine residue to PG (called lysinylation) and whose amino-terminal end has flipase activity, which is involved in the translocation of lysyl-PG from the inner to the outer side of the membrane (Miller et al., 2016). Multiple, so-called gain-of-function mutations in the *mprF* gene cause an amplification of the protein function, resulting in an increase in the positive charge on the outer side of the membrane, which repels the positively charged DAP-Ca complex and thus prevents its incorporation into the membrane (Miller et al., 2016; Bayer et al., 2015). An alternative pathway for increasing the positive membrane charge is mutations in the *dltABCD* operon leading to its overexpression or in the gene of the

Fig. 4. Structure of the daptomycin molecule representing the thirteen amino acid depsipeptide. (A) Chemical structure. (B) Amino acids present in the daptomycin structure. Unusual amino acids such as kynurenine (L-Kyn) and 3-methylglutamic acid (L-MeOGlu) play a key role in the antibacterial activity of daptomycin. L-Orn – ornithine.

two-component system GraSR, which is involved in *dlt* regulation (Cafiso et al., 2014). The *dlt* operon is responsible for the attachment of positively charged alanine to teichoic acid in the cell wall. Mutations that cause increased transcription of the *tagA* gene (Kattke et al., 2018), involved in teichoic acid synthesis, have also been described and, together with mutations in *dlt*, are associated with increased cell wall mass, another common phenotype in daptomycin resistance (Bertsche et al., 2013).

Another mechanism linked to daptomycin resistance in staphylococci is associated with point mutations in the *pgsA* and *cls2* genes and involves changes in membrane phospholipid composition (Gómez Casanova et al., 2017). *PgsA* encodes the enzyme CDP-diacylglycerol-3-phosphate-3-phosphatidyltransferase, which is responsible for catalysing the primary reaction in PG biosynthesis. Mutations in *pgsA* cause a decrease in the activity of the protein and thus a decrease in the total PG content in the cell membrane. *Cls2* encodes cardiolipin synthase, which is involved in cardiolipin synthesis by condensation of two PG molecules (Koprivnjak et al., 2011). Mutations in *cls2* are thought to increase the activity of the protein, which increases cardiolipin content in the membrane (Koprivnjak et al., 2011;

Lasek-Nesselquist et al., 2019). The increased amount of cardiolipin subsequently blocks the translocation of daptomycin aggregates, thereby promoting resistance (Zhang et al., 2014b).

Additional mutations involved in daptomycin resistance have been identified in the genes of the two-component regulatory systems *VraSR* and *WalKR* leading to increased peptidoglycan cross-linking and increased membrane fluidity (Miller et al., 2016). Mutations in the *rpoB* and *rpoC* genes encoding the β and β' subunits of RNA polymerase have also been described and are likely to contribute to both overproduction of *dlt* and increased positive membrane charge or cell wall thickening (Bæk et al., 2015). Since these mutations causing cell wall thickening are also associated with vancomycin resistance, very often GISA (glycopeptide-intermediate *S. aureus*) strains with increased MIC to daptomycin are thus isolated, although they were obtained from patients not treated with daptomycin (Miller et al., 2016; Howden et al., 2011). It is hypothesized that in the case of persistent bacteraemia daptomycin treatment failure may occur due to prior vancomycin therapy (Miller et al., 2016).

Furthermore, a 2016 study by Pader et al. described another mechanism by which resistant *S. aureus* may evade the effect of daptomycin,

namely the release of membrane phospholipids that sequester and inactivate daptomycin (Pader et al., 2016). This ability is impaired in wild-type bacteria (MSSA) by the production of small molecules of cytolytic toxins, which is triggered by the Agr quorum sensing system (Pee et al., 2018). These toxins likely compete with the antibiotic for binding to the phospholipid, thereby preventing daptomycin inactivation (Pader et al., 2016). Many *S. aureus* infections are caused by mutant strains with defective Agr systems and thus defective production of cytolytic enzymes (Pee et al., 2018). Such bacteria can then effectively inactivate daptomycin and develop a resistant phenotype even in heterogeneous populations with wild-type cells (Gray and Wenzel, 2020).

Thus, although daptomycin resistance is still rare, analysing and detecting the factors described, as well as finding suitable inhibitors of particular mechanisms (Pee et al., 2018), may reduce the likelihood of therapeutic failure.

3.4. Antibiotics inhibiting proteosynthesis on the ribosomal subunit 30S

3.4.1. Aminoglycoside antibiotics

Aminoglycosides are a group of broad-spectrum antibiotics first discovered in the 1940s and derived from actinomycetes. The first aminoglycoside, streptomycin, was isolated in 1944 from *Streptomyces griseus*. In the years since its discovery, other natural members of this class have been introduced, namely neomycin (1949), kanamycin (1957), gentamicin (1963) and tobramycin (1967) (Krause et al., 2016a). All the antibiotics named are produced by soil bacteria of the genus *Streptomyces* or *Micromonospora* and are therefore identified by the suffixes "-mycin" or "-micin" (Ramirez and Tolmasky, 2017a). Unfortunately, also with aminoglycosides, bacteria have evolved several mechanisms to resist their action. The primary mechanism of resistance is the acquisition of aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes (AMEs). The first such enzyme was identified in 1967 in *Escherichia coli* (Umezawa et al., 1967). Thus, to overcome resistance, semisynthetic derivatives that do not serve as substrates for most AMEs were developed in the 1970s (Ramirez and Tolmasky, 2017a). One of the most successful semisynthetic aminoglycosides, amikacin, was introduced in 1977 and is still used to treat a wide range of infections with great success (Ramirez and Tolmasky, 2017a). Aminoglycosides were widely used as first-line agents until the 1980s, but were superseded by the advent of other classes of less toxic antibiotics such as carbapenems, cephalosporins and fluoroquinolones (Krause et al., 2016a). In recent years, however, increasing multidrug resistance has renewed interest in aminoglycosides. A better dosing scheme (once-daily doses) has been developed to minimize their ototoxicity, nephrotoxicity and rare neuromuscular blockade while maintaining efficacy (Stankowicz et al., 2015). Due to their synergistic activity with cell wall synthesis inhibiting antibiotics, they have also started to be administered in combination antibiotic therapy with β -lactams, especially in suspected MDR bacteria and so-called difficult-to-treat infections (Serio et al., 2018a). Also in 2018, a new synthetic member of this class, plazomycin, was approved by the US Food and Drug Administration after almost 40 years since the introduction of aminoglycosides (Clark and Burgess, 2020). Although it has also been reported to show potent *in-vitro* synergistic activity in combination with ceftobiprole or daptomycin against MRSA and VRSA strains (Zhanel et al., 2012b), it has not yet been recommended for the treatment of staphylococcal infections.

Aminoglycosides act through inhibition of proteosynthesis. Their entry into the bacterial cell consists of three steps. In the first step (called energy-independent self-promoted uptake (Mingot-Leclercq et al., 1999)), ionic bond formation occurs between negatively charged groups present on the bacterial surface and polycationic hydrophobic molecules of aminoglycosides. Surface anionic compounds in the case of Gram-positive bacteria include mainly teichoic acid and phospholipids (Ramirez and Tolmasky, 2017b). The consequence of this interaction is the displacement of divalent cations (Mg^{2+}) leading to an increase in permeability and the beginning of aminoglycoside uptake (Zhanel et al.,

2012b). In the second phase (energy dependent phase I), aminoglycosides enter the cytoplasm via the proton motive force and the electron transport system (Serio et al., 2018b). This is the reason why aminoglycosides lack activity against anaerobic bacteria (Kong et al., 2020). In the cytoplasm, aminoglycosides affect proteosynthesis, leading to protein mistranslation. In the third and final step (energy dependent phase II), the aberrant proteins thus synthesized are inserted into the cytoplasmic membrane, damaging its integrity, and facilitating the entry of a large number of other aminoglycoside molecules (Webster and Shepherd, 2022). This results in a high level of errors in proteosynthesis, extensive membrane damage, uptake of additional molecules at an even higher rate, and subsequent cell death.

The aminoglycoside effect is exerted in the cytoplasm by binding to the A-site on the 16S rRNA of the 30S ribosomal subunit and altering its conformation (Krause et al., 2016b). The consequence of this interaction is the induction of misreading of aminoacyl-tRNA codons and the promotion of mistranslation (Krause et al., 2016a). Proteins with incorrect amino acids in the peptide sequence subsequently damage the cell membrane (Webster and Shepherd, 2022). Some aminoglycosides also directly inhibit translation initiation or elongation (Webster and Shepherd, 2022). Although individual aminoglycosides bind to different positions on the A-site and their action varies slightly according to their chemical structure, all aminoglycosides are bactericidal and are characterized by a long postantibiotic effect (Krause et al., 2016b; Wilson, 2014). The bactericidal activity provides aminoglycosides with a uniqueness, as all other antibiotics inhibiting proteosynthesis are bacteriostatic.

Mechanisms of resistance of aminoglycosides

There are several mechanisms of aminoglycoside resistance that can coexist in the same cell. Modification of aminoglycosides by aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes (AMEs) is the primary mechanism of resistance in both Gram-positive (including *S. aureus*) and Gram-negative bacteria (Ramirez and Tolmasky, 2010b). Other mechanisms, occurring predominantly in Gram-negative bacteria, include target site (16S rRNA) modification by methylation, chromosomal gene mutations, and active drug efflux (Doi et al., 2016).

Acquisition of AMEs is the most prevalent mechanism of aminoglycoside resistance worldwide, and the most important in *S. aureus*. Currently, more than 100 of such enzymes have been described. They are encoded by genes localized on transposons and plasmids that often encode other resistance genes and are therefore predominantly found in MDR bacteria. Clinical isolates usually have more than one AME encoding gene. AMEs catalyse the modification of hydroxyl or amine groups on the aminoglycoside molecule, which reduce the binding affinity of the antibiotic to the ribosome and lead to loss of antibacterial efficacy. The classification of AMEs is determined by their nomenclature. AMEs are divided into three classes based on their ability to phosphorylate (aminoglycoside O-phosphotransferase, APH), acetylate (aminoglycoside N-acetyltransferase, AAC) or adenylate (aminoglycoside O-nucleotidyl transferase, ANT) (Krause et al., 2016a). Individual classes are then subdivided into subclasses according to the number given in parentheses to indicate the site of modification (a particular carbon), followed by a single or double apostrophe (prime symbol) to symbolize that the reaction is taking place on the first or second sugar unit (Munita and Arias, 2016). In the case that there are multiple enzymes modifying the same site (isoenzymes), but their substrate specificity and selectivity differ (*i.e.* they provide a different resistance profile). Roman numerals and in some cases a lowercase letters are additionally provided to distinguish them as an individual enzyme identifier (Krause et al., 2016b; Ramirez and Tolmasky, 2010b).

The most important and commonly produced enzymes in *S. aureus* include AAC(6)Ie/APH(2)-Ia, APH(3)-IIIa, ANT(6)-Ia, ANT(9)-Ia, and ANT(4)-Ia localized on plasmids and transposons (Khosravi et al., 2017; Szymanek-Majchrzak et al., 2018).

Aminoglycoside acetyltransferases catalyse the acetylation of amine (-NH₂) groups on an antibiotic molecule using acetyl coenzyme A

(AcCoA) as a donor (Ramirez and Tolmasky, 2010b). The reaction can take place at four positions (1, 3, 2' and 6) of the aminoglycoside, and thus AAC enzymes are divided into four subclasses (Krause et al., 2016a). AAC(6) enzymes are the most abundant subclass and are present in both Gram-positive and negative bacteria. These enzymes can also exist as hybrids. An example is the bifunctional AAC(6)-Ie/APH(2)-Ia enzyme encoded by the *aac(6)-aph(2)* gene (sometimes referred to as *aacA-aphD*), which is highly prevalent in *S. aureus*, including MRSA, and *E. faecalis* (Szymanek-Majchrzak et al., 2018; Costa et al., 2019). It is one of the most clinically important AMEs (Frase et al., 2012). It is involved in resistance to gentamicin, kanamycin, tobramycin, netilmicin and amikacin, which it inactivates by phosphorylation and/or acetylation (Ramirez and Tolmasky, 2010b; Zárate et al., 2018). AAC activity is mediated by the N-terminal domain, while the C-terminal domain is involved in APH activity, and both domains can function independently (Frase et al., 2012). AAC(6)Ie/APH(2)-Ia is the only enzyme identified so far that causes gentamicin resistance in *S. aureus* due to phosphorylation.

Aminoglycoside phosphotransferases mediate aminoglycoside resistance by catalysing the transfer of a phosphate group from ATP (GTP (Frase et al., 2012)) to a hydroxyl group on the antibiotic molecule (Ramirez and Tolmasky, 2010a). The modification can take place at 7 positions (4, 6, 9, 3, 2', 3', 7), therefore APH enzymes are divided into seven subclasses. The APH(3)IIIa enzyme, encoded by the *aph(3)-IIIa* gene, is prevalent in Gram-positive bacteria, including MRSA, and causes resistance to kanamycin, neomycin, amikacin, and lividomycin (Serio et al., 2018a; Ramirez and Tolmasky, 2010b). APH(3)IIIa uses only ATP as a donor of the PO_4^{3-} group (Shakya and Wright, 2010). The phosphotransferase APH(2)Ia, which plays an important role in gentamicin resistance across Gram-positive bacteria, uses GTP as a donor substrate (Frase et al., 2012).

Aminoglycoside nucleotidyltransferases catalyse the transfer of an adenosine mono phosphate (AMP) group from an ATP donor to a hydroxyl group on an antibiotic molecule. A total of five positions can be modified (6, 9, 4, 2', 3) and thus ANT enzymes are divided into five subclasses (Ramirez and Tolmasky, 2010a). The most abundant ANT enzyme in *S. aureus*, including MRSA, is ANT(4)-Ia encoded by the *ant(4)-Ia* gene (sometimes referred to as *aadD*) (Khosravi et al., 2017). It is carried on a plasmid and confers resistance to kanamycin, tobramycin, neomycin, and amikacin. Other important staphylococcal enzymes of this class include ANT(6)-Ia (encoded by the *ant(6)-Ia* gene, sometimes referred to as *ant6* or *aadE*) and ANT(9)-Ia (encoded by the *ant(9)-Ia* gene, sometimes referred to as *spc* or *aad(9)*) (Ramirez and Tolmasky, 2010a). While ANT(6)-Ia confers resistance to streptomycin (Zárate et al., 2018), ANT(9)-Ia confers resistance to spectinomycin (Kanchugal P and Selmer, 2020).

Due to their broad spectrum of activity and rapid bactericidal effect, aminoglycosides occupy a very important position among clinically used antibiotics. Although their position has been eroded due to the availability of less toxic antibiotics, dosage adjustments and the approval of plazomicin (Cox et al., 2018) for clinical use have renewed interest in this class. Today, within aminoglycoside antibiotics, attention is focused on the development of a new generation of aminoglycosides (the so-called neoglycosides (Rocha et al., 2021); Labby and Garneau-Tsodikova, 2013) that possess lower toxicity, reduced sensitivity to AMEs, and enhanced antibacterial activity (Rocha et al., 2021; Quirke et al., 2022; Yan et al., 2022). Another promising strategy to overcome resistance caused by modifying enzymes is the search for their inhibitors (Labby and Garneau-Tsodikova, 2013). Inhibitors could thus become adjuvants that would be delivered in combination with the antibiotic in question (Costa et al., 2020). The first efforts to develop such inhibitors began several decades ago with the discovery that AcCoA serves as a co-substrate for AAC enzymes (Williams and Northrop, 1979). Subsequently, bisubstrate inhibitors such as a gentamicin derivative with AcCoA attached were developed (Williams and Northrop,

1979). However, such agents were mostly unsuccessful in in-vivo assays, probably due to the large molecular size and low membrane permeability (Labby and Garneau-Tsodikova, 2013). Nowadays, in combination therapy for aminoglycosides, research focuses on cationic peptides, natural products with/without antibacterial activity and combination of antibiotics with nanomaterials (Rocha et al., 2021; Labby and Garneau-Tsodikova, 2013; Yan et al., 2022; Costa et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2022a).

3.4.2. Tetracycline antibiotics

Tetracyclines were introduced in the 1940s and represent an important class of broad-spectrum antibiotics. They are active against a large number of Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria and spirochetes, as well as parasites, protozoa or intracellular organisms (Grossman, 2016). The first tetracycline discovered (1948) and approved for clinical use was chlortetracycline produced by *Streptomyces aureofaciens* (Duggar, 1948). Soon thereafter, other natural substances produced by actinomycetes, oxytetracycline (1950) and tetracycline (1953), were isolated and together with chlortetracycline represent the first generation of tetracyclines (Finlay et al., 1950; Nelson and Levy, 2011). Following these discoveries, intensive development of other tetracyclines was initiated that would exhibit better pharmacokinetic properties, less toxicity, and a broader spectrum of action (McCormick et al., 1957). Thus, a second generation of tetracyclines was introduced, which included semisynthetic doxycycline (1967) and minocycline (1972) (Nelson and Levy, 2011). However, the rapid spread of antibiotic resistance and the emergence of MDR pathogens limited the clinical use of these "older" tetracyclines to the treatment of tetracycline-susceptible infections (Grossman, 2016). Efforts to further develop so-called modern tetracyclines were renewed in the late 1980s (Grossman, 2016). The development focused on the gain of new derivatives by modification of the C7 and C9 positions in the tetracycline structure led to the discovery of a new subclass of tetracyclines, the so-called glycylicyclines (Rusu and Buta, 2021). In 2006, the FDA approved the first member of this subclass, tigecycline, which was also the first tetracycline approved in more than 30 years (Stein and Craig, 2006). In recent years, the approval (2018) of other modern tetracyclines, omadacycline and eravacycline, has been considered the greatest success (Gallagher, 2019; Coppock, 2018). These, together with tigecycline, belong to the third generation of tetracyclines, which retain activity against MDR pathogens expressing tetracycline resistance determinants. Omadacycline has been approved for the treatment of community-acquired bacterial pneumonia and skin and soft tissue infections, and eravacycline is used to treat complicated intra-abdominal infections (Coppock, 2018; Durães and Sousa, 2019). In addition to their spectrum of activity, an important feature is the possibility of both intravenous and oral administration, which could allow outpatient treatment or shortened hospital stays, thus reducing costs (Rusu and Buta, 2021; Gallagher, 2019).

Tetracyclines act bacteriostatically in the same way as aminoglycosides, through inhibition of proteosynthesis. In Gram-positive bacteria, tetracyclines enter the cell by active transport and/or passive diffusion. In the cytoplasm, individual molecules form complexes with Mg^{2+} and in this form bind with high affinity to a position that overlaps with the A-site on the 16S rRNA of the 30S ribosomal subunit (Grossman, 2016). At this position, the antibiotic molecule serves as a steric hindrance and prevents the binding of the incoming aminoacyl-tRNA to the A-site, thereby inhibiting the elongation step of translation and thus overall protein synthesis.

Mechanisms of resistance of tetracyclines

Resistance to tetracyclines is commonly associated with the acquisition of mobile genetic elements that carry specific resistance genes. To date, 63 such genes have been identified and are summarized in the Nomenclature for Tetracycline Genes maintained at the University of Washington (<http://faculty.washington.edu/marilynr/>; last updated April 2021). The proteins encoded by these genes function by three mechanisms: efflux, ribosomal protection, and enzymatic inactivation,

the first two of which are responsible for clinically important MDR bacteria including *S. aureus*. The efflux of tetracycline pumps will be discussed in detail in Chapter 3.7, and therefore the following text will focus primarily on the mechanisms of ribosome protection and tetracycline destructase.

Ribosomal protection proteins (RPPs) function as molecular shields that prevent tetracyclines from binding to their target site by direct physical interaction with the ribosome while hydrolysing GTP, thereby neutralizing their inhibitory effects on protein synthesis. To date, 13 such proteins have been described, and their genes have been found in a wide range of bacterial species, as they are often encoded on plasmids and conjugative transposons (Roberts, 2023). The most widely used and studied proteins to date are Tet(O) and Tet(M), showing 75 % sequence similarity to each other. Tet(M) is by far the most abundant RPP to tetracyclines in clinical isolates of streptococci, enterococci, and staphylococci (including MRSA isolates) (Wilson et al., 2020). Tet(O) and Tet(M) belong to the superfamily of translation factor GTPases and share significant structural and sequence similarities with elongation factors Tu (EF-Tu) and G (EF-G) used in proteosynthesis (Ero et al., 2021).

Several studies using cryo-electron microscopy have addressed the precise functioning of Tet(M) (Dönhöfer et al., 2012; Connell et al., 2003; Arenz et al., 2015). Tet(O) and other RPPs are predicted to function by a very similar mechanism. Tet(M) physically protects the ribosome from the inhibitory effects of tetracycline by directly binding to a target site overlapping with the binding site for tetracycline and causing destabilization of the tetracycline-ribosome complex. Tet(M) binds to the ribosome in a post-translocation state. It uses Pro509 in loop III of domain IV of Tet(M) to do this, which interacts with nucleobase C1054 of the 16S rRNA (part of the primary binding site for tetracycline) and induces a change in its conformation (Arenz et al., 2015). This change disrupts the stacking interaction between C1054 and the aromatic ring of tetracyclines and causes dissociation of tetracyclines from the ribosome (Dönhöfer et al., 2012). Further, the binding of the C-terminal extension in Tet(M) interacts with A1492 and A1493 to induce their inverted conformation, which promotes rapid binding of the ternary complex, thereby restoring proteosynthesis (Dönhöfer et al., 2012). These conformational changes are permanent and prevent tetracycline re-binding. However, the question remains as to when exactly GTP hydrolysis occurs. The prevailing view is that hydrolysis is used for the conformational changes and subsequent dissociation of Tet(M) from the ribosome rather than for the release of tetracycline itself. This has been confirmed by experiments where tetracycline release also occurred using non-hydrolysable GTP analogues (Dönhöfer et al., 2012; Burdett, 1996)].

These RPPs confer resistance mainly to the classical tetracyclines (tetracycline, doxycycline and minocycline). Third-generation tetracyclines retain their activity in the presence of Tet(M) and Tet(O). This fact is attributed to the C9-side chain on the aromatic ring of these derivatives, which not only increases the binding affinity to the ribosome but also prevents the nucleotides of loop III of RPPs from accessing C1054 (Wilson et al., 2020; Arenz et al., 2015).

Another known mechanism of resistance to tetracyclines is mediated by the so-called tetracycline destructase Tet(X), the action of which has so far been reported against tigecycline (Nguyen et al., 2014). It is a flavin-dependent monooxygenase that inactivates tigecycline by hydroxylation at the C_{11a} position, leading to non-enzymatic degradation of this unstable compound (Zhang et al., 2022).

3.5. Antibiotics inhibiting proteosynthesis on the ribosomal subunit 50S

One of the key structures on which antibiotics act is the large ribosomal subunit. There are several major classes of antibiotics whose action is exerted through inhibition of the 50S subunit of the ribosome. Since these antibiotics often share the same resistance mechanisms (same resistance determinants), they will be discussed together in this separate chapter.

3.5.1. Antibiotics of the macrolide-linkosamide-streptogramin type B (MLS_B) class

Macrolides are a class of antibiotics known for their broad-spectrum activity. They are effective against Gram-positive bacteria, including *Staphylococcus aureus*, and some atypical bacteria, such as *Mycoplasma pneumoniae* or *Chlamydia pneumoniae*, but activity against Gram-negative bacteria is generally limited. In their structure, they are characterized by a macrocyclic lactone ring that typically contains 14–16 carbon atoms, combined with deoxy or amino sugar residues (Kannan and Mankin, 2011). Macrolides are used to treat a variety of bacterial infections, including respiratory tract infections, skin and soft tissue infections, sinusitis, and some sexually transmitted infections. In some cases, they are also used as an alternative treatment for patients with penicillin allergy.

Macrolide antibiotics have a rich history of development, leading to three generations of macrolides, each with improved properties and an expanded antibacterial spectrum. Erythromycin was the first macrolide to be discovered and introduced into clinical use in the early 1950s. It was isolated from the bacterium *Streptomyces erythraeus*. Its short biological half-life and frequent side effects led to the development of a second, so-called "side-effect-free" generation of macrolides, semi-synthetic derivatives such as clarithromycin or azithromycin, to overcome these limitations (Miklasińska-Majdanik, 2021). Clarithromycin has higher stability in acidic environments and better bioavailability. It has also extended the spectrum of activity to include some Gram-negative bacteria. Azithromycin has gained popularity due to its unique property, namely its long biological half-life, which allows once-daily use. Third generation macrolides were developed in response to increasing resistance to lower generation macrolides. It is represented by a class of ketolides that is structurally related to them - it contains a keto group replacing the C3 cladinose of erythromycin. An important representative was telithromycin, but its use has been sharply restricted in many countries because of concerns about hepatotoxicity. Currently, macrolides are used only on a limited basis for staphylococcal infections. Erythromycin still has a place in the treatment of infections caused by MSSA strains, while clarithromycin and azithromycin have more clinical use in the treatment of infections caused by bacteria other than *S. aureus*.

Linkosamides are composed of a central amino acid moiety linked by an amide bond to a sugar molecule. Their story begins with the discovery of lincomycin in the late 1950s. Lincomycin was originally isolated from the bacterium *Streptomyces lincolnensis*, which was found in soil samples from Lincoln, Nebraska, USA (Schwarz et al., 2016). Lincomycin was first introduced for clinical use in the early 1960s. It showed excellent activity against Gram-positive bacteria, including *Streptococcus* and *Staphylococcus* species. In the 1970s, researchers began synthesizing derivatives of lincomycin to improve its pharmacological properties and spectrum of activity. Clindamycin was developed, which had better oral bioavailability and was effective against a wider range of pathogens. Clindamycin quickly gained popularity for its efficacy against Gram-positive bacteria, including MSSA and MRSA infections, and became widely used in clinical practice. In the 1980s and subsequent decades, more refined formulations and dosing regimens for clindamycin were developed to maximize its therapeutic benefits. Today, it remains an important antibiotic in the treatment of various bacterial infections.

Streptogramins are a class of antibiotics used in the treatment of various bacterial infections, primarily those caused by Gram-positive bacteria. They are often reserved for serious infections or when other antibiotics prove ineffective. Streptogramins are actually divided into two subgroups: streptogramin A and streptogramin B, each with its own mechanism of action. They are often administered in combination because they show a synergistic effect when used together. Their unique mechanism of action and the synergy between the components make them valuable, especially in the treatment of infections with multidrug-resistant bacterial strains such as VRSA and MRSA. Streptogramins A have a macrocyclic ring in their structure with peptide and lactone

linkages. Their members include pristinamycin IIA, virginiamycin M, and dalfopristin. Streptogramins B are hexadepsipeptides and are represented by, e.g., pristinamycin IA, virginiamycin S, or quinupristin. Streptogramin antibiotics are represented by pristinamycin, virginiamycin, or the most prominent member quinupristin/dalfopristin, which is the only one approved by the FDA for the treatment of bacterial infections in humans. Under the trade name Synercid, it has become a valuable addition to the antibiotic armamentarium and represents one of the limited antimicrobial options available for the treatment of human infections caused by multidrug-resistant pathogens such as MRSA, VISA, VRSA or vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus faecalis*. However, its limitation is the possibility of intravenous administration only.

Mechanism of action of MLS_B group antibiotics

MLS_B antibiotics bind to the 23S rRNA of the 50S ribosomal subunit. The binding sites of these antibiotics often overlap and therefore act by a very similar mechanism, namely by causing premature dissociation of peptidyl-tRNA from the ribosome. The primary binding site for macrolides is the nascent peptide exit tunnel (NPET) near the peptidyl transferase center (PTC), which is critical for peptide bond formation during protein synthesis. The C₅ side chain of macrolides interacts with nucleotides A2058 and 2059 in domain V, and rarely with nucleotide A752 in domain II. This binding prevents newly synthesized polypeptides from leaving the ribosome via NPET and terminates elongation in the first rounds of proteosynthesis (Kannan and Mankin, 2011). Thus, erythromycin causes dissociation of peptidyl-tRNAs carrying 6–8 amino acid residues, while ketolides, which lack cladinose, allow polymerization of 9–10 amino acid residues (Tenson et al., 2003). The binding site of macrolides also overlaps with the binding site of streptogramins B. These act synergistically with streptogramins A, which bind at the PTC site where they inhibit peptide bond formation while altering the rRNA conformation, which subsequently allows for stronger streptogramin B binding at the beginning of NPET (Foster, 2017).

Streptogramins B, such as pristinamycin IA, then cause dissociation of peptidyl-tRNAs of 6 amino acid residues. Lincosamides have an overlapping binding site with streptogramins A, where they inhibit the peptidyl transferase reaction at the PTC center, causing polymerization of only 2–4 amino acid residues (Schwarz et al., 2016).

Mechanisms of resistance of MLS_B group antibiotics

Macrolide resistance is now prevalent worldwide, with a significant proportion of staphylococci showing so-called cross-resistance to all MLS_B group antibiotics. This is mainly due to shared binding sites for the action of individual antibiotics. There are three main mechanisms of resistance in this group of drugs, namely target site (ribosome) modification, ribosome protection/efflux of antibiotics from the cell, and synthesis of inactivating enzymes, with the first two being the dominant mechanisms in clinical isolates (Miklasińska-Majdanik, 2021). The resistance genes to MLS_B antibiotics are carried by various transposons, plasmids, or gene islands, and their transfer via HGT is very easy (Feßler et al., 2018). Moreover, these mechanisms may exhibit distinct resistance phenotypes, for which correct interpretation is extremely important for selecting appropriate treatment and preventing the spread of resistance.

The first type of resistance mechanism, antibiotic binding site modification, in *S. aureus* is caused by the adenylyl-N-methyltransferase enzyme, encoded by the erythromycin ribosomal methylation genes (*erm* genes) *ermA*, *ermB* and *ermC*. The Erm enzyme is responsible for the dimethylation of adenine A2058 in 23S rRNA, i.e. part of the binding site for macrolides, which subsequently cannot bind to the modified ribosome. Expression of *erm* genes may be constitutive or inducible, modulating the resulting resistance phenotype. The first type is based on active mRNA, which leads to constitutive methyltransferase synthesis and causes resistance to all MLS_B antibiotics (cMLS_B phenotype) (Miklasińska-Majdanik, 2021). Inducible resistance expression involves inactive mRNA, which needs to be activated by the presence of an appropriate inducer, most commonly macrolides with 14 carbon atoms

excluding ketolides (e.g., erythromycin) or with 15 carbon atoms (e.g., azithromycin). This type of expression manifests as the iMLS_B phenotype, which confers resistance only to inducers that trigger methyltransferase synthesis (Miklasińska-Majdanik, 2021). Resistance to other macrolides, lincosamides, and type B streptogramins occurs only in the presence of concomitant use of the inducer and these antibiotics.

The most abundant gene of all *erm* genes in *S. aureus* is *ermC*, followed by *ermA*, in both resistance phenotypes (Miklasińska-Majdanik, 2021). *ErmB* is a minority gene in *S. aureus* and is much more present in the genomes of enterococci and streptococci. *ErmC* and *ermA* are most commonly expressed inducibly, as this is more advantageous for the bacteria. Strains with constitutive expression evolve primarily in the *ermC* gene as a result of insertions, duplications, deletions and, in limited numbers, point mutations (most commonly at the 5' end of the gene). The expression of *ermA* and *ermC* within the iMLS_B phenotype is regulated at the level of translation - the *ermA* gene is preceded by two genes, *pepL* and *pepI*, encoding leading peptides, whereas *ermC* is preceded by only one, the *pep* gene (Mlynarczyk-Bonikowska et al., 2022). In the absence of inducers, translated leader peptides interact with mRNA and prevent translation of Erm methyltransferase by preventing ribosome access to their binding site. In the event that an inducer (e.g., erythromycin) binds to the ribosome, the translation of the guide peptides is blocked and the mRNA conformation is altered, subsequently allowing Erm methyltransferase synthesis.

A representative of the second major mechanism of macrolide resistance is the product of *msrA* gene, which encodes an adenosine triphosphate-binding cassette transport protein of the ATP-binding cassette subfamily F (ABC-F) (Feßler et al., 2018; Galarion et al., 2023). Msr proteins are divided into 4 classes: A, C, D and E, but only MsrA can be present in the *S. aureus* genome. This protein causes resistance to macrolides and type B streptogramins and thus is characterized by another resistance phenotype referred to as MS_B. The mechanism of action of ABC-F proteins was highly debated. Two hypotheses had been proposed, each of which had considerable support. Initially, ABC-F proteins were thought to function as efflux pumps, but in recent years it has been proved, that they play a role as ribosomal protection proteins (Sharkey et al., 2016; Ero et al., 2019). ABC-F proteins consist of two nucleotide binding domains. However, unlike efflux pumps, they are neither fused to nor genetically associated with two other transmembrane domains (TMDs) localized in the cytoplasmic membrane (Sharkey et al., 2016). Additionally, the ABC-F protein class has also been shown to include other *S. aureus* resistance-conferring proteins that function as RPPs (Galarion et al., 2023; Sharkey et al., 2016; Vimberg et al., 2020a). These are the determinants Vga (resistance to lincosamides and type A streptogramins, LS_A resistance phenotype) and Lsa (resistance to lincosamides, type A streptogramins and pleuromutilins, LS_AP phenotype) (Ero et al., 2021; Sharkey et al., 2016). Thus, these proteins, as with MsrA, are thought to overlap their binding site with that of the antibiotic and use ATP to produce conformational changes that destabilize the antibiotic and displace it or prevent its binding altogether.

A third mechanism of resistance is represented by *S. aureus* enzymes inactivating macrolide antibiotics, but their occurrence is not so frequent as to rise concern in the clinical setting. The first group of genes involved are erythromycin esterase (*ere*) genes, which hydrolytically degrade macrolides with 14 and 15 carbon atoms. The second group of genes encodes Mph phosphotransferases. Although 7 such phosphotransferases are known, only the MphB and MphC proteins carried by the *mphB* and *mphC* genes cause macrolide resistance of 14, 15 and 16 carbon macrolides in *S. aureus*. These enzymes phosphorylate the 2'-OH sugar group, which is important for the formation of the linkage between the antibiotic and nucleotide A2058 (Miklasińska-Majdanik, 2021). Virginiamycin B lyases (Vgb) are also known to linearize the cyclic B-type streptogramin molecule, inactivating it and conferring the S_B resistance phenotype (Foster, 2017).

Thus, for MLS_B antibiotics, the correct interpretation of the

resistance phenotype is of utmost importance for the selection of appropriate treatment. In the case of macrolide/lincosamide resistance, EUCAST recommends the use of a standardized disc diffusion method to distinguish iMLS_B, cMLS_B and MS_B phenotypes from each other (Fig. 5) (EUCAST Clinical Breakpoint Tables, 2024). The results should then be confirmed by testing MIC values.

3.5.2. Antibiotics of the class phenicol-linkosamides-oxazolidinones-pleuromutilins-streptogramins type A (PhLOPS_A)

Phenicol antibiotics are a class of antibiotics that includes drugs derived from chloramphenicol, a natural antibiotic originally isolated from the bacterium *Streptomyces venezuelae* (Izard, 2001). Chloramphenicol itself, along with its derivatives, florfenicol and thiamphenicol, exhibit broad-spectrum antibacterial activity. While chloramphenicol, florfenicol and thiamphenicol share a common structural class, it is essential to note that their clinical use may differ due to differences in pharmacokinetics, side effect profiles and availability. The use of chloramphenicol is limited in many regions due to its potential for rare but serious adverse effects including blood disorders (e.g., bone marrow suppression). Thus, its use is now limited and generally reserved for situations where other antibiotics are ineffective or contraindicated, for the treatment of a small number of life-threatening infections, or for topical applications (Schwarz et al., 2016). Thiamphenicol and florfenicol were developed to preserve antibacterial efficacy while reducing some of the toxicities associated with chloramphenicol. Today, however, these antibiotics are used in veterinary medicine.

Oxazolidinones represent a new class of antibiotics that was introduced shortly before 2000 and includes completely synthetic antibiotics (Izard, 2001). Their structure is characterized by the presence of an oxazolidine ring. Oxazolidinones were developed in response to the growing challenge of antibiotic-resistant bacteria. An example of oxazolidinone antibiotics is linezolid, discovered in 1996 and approved for clinical use in 2000 (FDA) (Foti et al., 2021). Linezolid has demonstrated potent activity against Gram-positive bacteria, including drug-resistant strains such as MRSA. Its success marked a milestone in the development of antibiotics and offers an effective treatment option for various infections, especially difficult-to-treat nosocomial diseases such as catheter-related infections, etc. Over time, concerns about resistance emerged, prompting ongoing research to refine existing compounds and explore new derivatives within the oxazolidinone class. Thus, in 2014, tedizolid, a second-generation oxazolidinone, was approved by both the FDA and EMA for the treatment of acute bacterial infections of the skin and soft tissues. Tedizolid has a broad spectrum of efficacy, particularly against resistant forms of bacteria such as staphylococci resistant to vancomycin, daptomycin and linezolid, or multidrug-resistant enterococci and streptococci. Today, at least four other novel oxazolidinones (i.

e. sutezolid, contezolid, radezolid, delpazolid) are being investigated in clinical trials (Foti et al., 2021).

Pleuromutilins are antibacterial agents, semisynthetic derivatives of the naturally occurring diterpene pleuromutilin first isolated from the fungus *Pleurotus mutilus* in the 1950s (Paukner and Riedl, 2017). In the years since that discovery, thiamulin and valnemulin have been introduced and have applications only in veterinary medicine. Thus, research in the field of pleuromutilins has continued with the aim of discovering new compounds, or optimizing existing ones, for the treatment of bacterial human infections. This resulted in the approval of retapamulin for clinical use in the treatment of bacterial skin infections, particularly impetigo, and other uncomplicated skin infections caused by susceptible strains of bacteria. It is administered topically in the form of an ointment. The most advanced compound, lefamulin, was also approved in 2019 (US) and 2020 (EU) for the treatment of systemic infections such as community-acquired bacterial pneumonia (Paukner and Riedl, 2017; Zhanel et al., 2021). It is available for oral but also intravenous administration.

Mechanism of action of PhLOPS_A group antibiotics

The mechanism of action is almost identical to that of MLS_B group antibiotics, as are their binding sites on the ribosome. Retapamulin has an overlapping site with A-type streptogramins and clindamycin, i.e. it binds in PTC to the A-site overlapping the P-site and thus inhibits aminoacyl-tRNA binding and peptide bond formation. Linezolid, tedizolid and chloramphenicol have overlapping binding sites in the PTC at the A-site where they inhibit peptidyl transferase activity and peptide bond formation.

Mechanisms of resistance of PhLOPS_A group antibiotics

This group has a variety of resistance mechanisms providing an additional number of resistance spectra (phenotypes), as does the MLS_B group. These again include target site modification, ribosomal protection, enzymatic inactivation and mutational changes.

The first resistance mechanism mentioned includes the Chloramphenicol-Floramphenicol Resistant Protein (Cfr) encoded by the *cfr* gene. Its name consists of the two antibiotics with which the resistance conferred was associated, but it was later found that the resistance phenotype of this protein encompasses the entire PhLOPS_A family of antibiotics. Cfr is an adenylyl-N-methyltransferase catalyzing the C₈ dimethylation of nucleotide A2503. Thus, it modifies a common part of the overlapping binding sites of PhLOPS_A antibiotics that can no longer bind to the ribosome in this state.

Additional resistance phenotypes are conferred by a group of ribosomal protection proteins, specifically the Lsa, Sal, Vga, OptrA and PoxTA proteins. As mentioned in the previous chapter, these enzymes are among the ABC-F proteins that have overlapping binding sites with the respective antibiotics and alter the conformation of the ribosomes in an

Fig. 5. Detection of macrolide and lincosamide resistance phenotypes using the disk diffusion method. (A) Phenotype of MS_B resistance where a completely circular zone of inhibition of the clindamycin disk is visible. (B) Constitutive MLS_B phenotype with no formation of inhibition zones around any disc. (C) Phenotype of inducible MLS_B resistance, where there is a flattening of the inhibition zone of the clindamycin disk (the so-called D-zone). Cli – clindamycin, Ery – erythromycin.

ATP-dependent manner, thus being able to displace these antibiotics from the ribosome and prevent their re-binding. This energy-driven process thus allows the bacterium to maintain protein synthesis in the presence of inhibitory concentrations of antibiotics. Thus, ABC-F proteins can confer resistance to almost all antibiotics that inhibit proteosynthesis. The individual proteins found in *S. aureus* include LsaE and Sal conferring the LSA_P resistance phenotype (lincosamides, type A streptogramins and pleuromutilins), Vga(A), (B), (C), (E) with the LSA resistance phenotype (lincosamides and type A streptogramins), and OptrA and PoxA proteins with the OPh resistance phenotype (oxazolidinones and phenicols) (Jensen and Lyon, 2009; Foster, 2017; Ero et al., 2021; Mohamad et al., 2022).

Within antibiotic inactivating enzymes, it is worth mentioning the proteins Virginiamycin A acetyltransferase (Vat) A and B encoded by the *vat(A)* and *vat(B)* genes, which are involved in the acetylation of the hydroxyl group on the streptogramin A molecule, rendering it ineffective. This group of mechanisms also includes the inactivation of chloramphenicol by chloramphenicol acetyltransferase (CAT) enzymes. These enzymes catalyse the acetylation of chloramphenicol, rendering it inactive and preventing it from binding effectively to the bacterial ribosome. CAT enzymes are divided into two types. Classical CAT enzymes are encoded by the *catA* genes detected across both Gram-positive and negative bacteria. Chloramphenicol resistance in *S. aureus* tends to be caused by their CAT A7, A8 and A9 subtypes carried on plasmids. The second type of CAT enzymes is encoded by the *catB* genes. In general, the resistance conferred by CAT B proteins is much lower than that of CAT A (based on MIC values) and so it is thought that they might play a different role for the bacterium (Schwarz et al., 2016).

An overview of individual resistance determinants, their mechanism of action and the provided resistance phenotype is shown in Table 1.

3.6. Other antibiotics inhibiting proteosynthesis

3.6.1. Mupirocin

Mupirocin, also known as pseudomonic acid, was discovered in the late 1970s by researchers studying soil bacteria. The antibiotic was initially isolated from a bacterial strain of *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, which produces it as a mixture of 4 pseudomonic acids (A-D). Pseudomonic acid A is the main compound of mupirocin (represents 90–95 %). The basic structure of pseudomonic acid consists of a monic acid with a pyran ring, which is attached via an ester linkage to a 9-hydroxynonaonic acid (Khoshnood et al., 2019).

The discovery of mupirocin marked a significant advancement in the field of antibiotics due to its unique structure, mechanism of action and

efficacy against *Staphylococcus aureus*. It is valued in treating skin and soft tissue infections, for its role in decolonizing MRSA carriers and for use as a prevention of recurring infections (Westgeest et al., 2024). Mupirocin is typically applied topically in the form of an ointment or cream.

Mupirocin acts in the cytoplasm and its target protein is isoleucyl-tRNA synthetase (IleRS). The mupirocin epoxy side chain shows structural similarity to isoleucine, due to which it binds to the active site of IleRS (into the isoleucine-specific binding pocket). The formation of isoleucine-charged tRNA is blocked, resulting in depletion of its cellular level, inhibition of proteosynthesis and subsequent bacterial death (Khoshnood et al., 2019; Tucaliuc et al., 2019). Mupirocin exhibits a high level of specificity for bacterial IleRS and has minimal activity against the mammalian (or eukaryotic) version of this enzyme. This selective action is a key reason why mupirocin is effective as an antibiotic for treating bacterial infections with low toxicity to human cells.

Mechanisms of resistance of mupirocin

Mupirocin resistance in *Staphylococcus aureus* was first reported in the late 1980s, shortly after the antibiotic began to be widely used. It typically arises through two primary mechanisms: chromosome-encoded low-level resistance (MIC 8–256 mg/l) and plasmid-encoded high-level resistance (MIC > 512 mg/l) (Dadashi et al., 2020).

Low-level resistance to mupirocin is associated with mutations in the native *ileRS* gene, which encodes the bacterial IleRS. Common point mutations are V588F and V631F, which cause changes in the mupirocin-binding site of IleRS reducing its affinity for mupirocin while still allowing it to function for protein synthesis (Wang et al., 2022b). Bacteria with low-level mupirocin resistance may still be inhibited by higher concentrations of the drug, but the effectiveness of standard therapeutic doses may be reduced.

High-level mupirocin resistance is primarily mediated by the acquisition of a plasmid-borne gene, *mupA* (also referred to as *ileRS2*), or the less common *mupB* gene (with 65 % sequence similarity to *mupA* and 45 % to *ileRS*). These genes encode a modified version of IleRS that has a very low affinity for mupirocin, effectively rendering the antibiotic ineffective.

3.6.2. Fusidic acid

Fusidic acid is a narrow-spectrum antibiotic derived from the fermentation of *Fusidium coccineum*, a soil-dwelling fungus. Introduced in the 1960s, fusidic acid is widely used, particularly in dermatology, for its potent activity against Gram-positive bacteria, most notably *S. aureus*. It is unique among antibiotics because of its steroid-like structure, though it does not have steroidal activity. It is commonly

Table 1

Resistance mechanisms and provided resistance phenotypes for antibiotics inhibiting proteosynthesis on the ribosomal subunit 50S. R - resistant.

Antibiotics inhibiting proteosynthesis on the ribosomal subunit 50S									
Gene	Resistance mechanism	Resistance phenotype	Macrolides	Streptogramins B	Lincosamides	Streptogramins A	Phenicols	Pleuromutilins	Oxazolidinones
<i>erm</i>	rRNA methyltransferase	MLS _B	R	R	R				
<i>cfr</i>	rRNA methyltransferase	PhLOPS _A			R	R	R	R	R
<i>msr</i>	Ribosomal protection	MS _B	R	R					
<i>vga</i>	Ribosomal protection	LS _A			R	R			
<i>lsa, sal</i>	Ribosomal protection	LS _A P			R	R		R	
<i>optr, pox</i>	Ribosomal protection	OPh			R		R		
<i>ere, mph</i>	Enzymatic inactivation	M	R						
<i>vgb</i>	Enzymatic inactivation	S _B		R					
<i>vat</i>	Enzymatic inactivation	S _A				R			

prescribed for conditions such as impetigo, infected dermatitis, folliculitis, and boils, typically in topical forms like creams and ointments. In addition to skin infections, fusidic acid is also used in managing deeper infections like osteomyelitis and septic arthritis. Due to its excellent tissue penetration and specific activity against *S. aureus*, fusidic acid is also a valuable option in cases where methicillin resistance is present. However, during treatment, a single point mutation is often enough to develop resistance, so fusidic acid is often used in the treatment of serious MRSA infections in combination with other antibiotics, e.g., rifampin.

Fusidic acid inhibits bacterial protein synthesis by targeting elongation factor G (EF-G), a protein essential for the translocation phase of translation. EF-G facilitates the movement of the mRNA-tRNA complex from the A-site to the P-site on the ribosome during protein synthesis. Fusidic acid binds specifically to EF-G when it is attached to the ribosome. The bond forms in the pocket between domains I to III (which forms after GTP hydrolysis) where it locks EF-G in place by preventing the conformational changes required for its dissociation. This inhibits the translocation step and effectively stops peptide chain elongation (González-López et al., 2024).

Despite fusidic acid clinical utility, the widespread use of this antibiotic has led to the emergence of resistant *S. aureus* strains. Resistance to fusidic acid can develop through two main mechanisms, including point mutations, as well as the acquisition of target protection proteins.

The first case involves mutations in the drug target EF-G gene (*fusA*). *FusA* mutations confer high-level resistance (MIC >64 mg/l) and in clinical isolates include for example H457Q, V90L, H457Q and L461K. However, some single mutations (e.g., L461K) may confer resistance with MIC > 256 mg/l (Fernandes, 2016). Other mutations that may occur and confer resistance, although rarely, involve the *fusE* gene. *FusE* variants carry frameshift or truncations in the *rplF* gene encoding ribosomal protein L6 (González-López et al., 2024). This protein is located near the binding site for EF-G on the ribosome. Its position helps to stabilize the ribosomal structure and supports EF-G function during translation. Therefore, mutations in *rplF* affect the binding of antibiotics such as fusidic acid.

The second type of resistance mechanism is the horizontal acquisition of the *fusB* or *fusC* gene. *FusB* is encoded on plasmids or chromosomal gene islands and *fusC* is carried within the staphylococcal cassette chromosome. *FusB* binds to EF-G and induces conformational changes in its domains (IV and V) and also affects the dynamics of domain III, ultimately allowing the release of EF-G from the ribosome (Ero et al., 2021; González-López et al., 2024). At the same time, fusidic acid dissociates from free EF-G due to low affinity (Ero et al., 2021; Fernandes, 2016).

3.7. Antibiotics inhibiting nucleic acid synthesis

Inhibition of nucleic acid synthesis is one of the key mechanisms of action of some antibiotics. These drugs interfere with the processes of DNA replication and RNA transcription, ultimately leading to disruption of bacterial cell growth and function. This class of antibiotics includes quinolones, sulfonamides, trimethoprim and rifamycins.

3.7.1. Quinolones

Quinolones are bactericidal broad-spectrum chemotherapeutic agents that were discovered in 1962 (nalidixic acid) and primarily target Gram-negative bacteria (Leshner et al., 1962). There are several generations of these drugs. The most significant modification of the structure was the introduction of a fluorine at the C₆ position and a major substituent at the C₇ position, hence this group is often referred to as fluoroquinolones (Correia et al., 2017). The second generation of fluoroquinolones includes ciprofloxacin, ofloxacin and norfloxacin and occupies a broader spectrum compared to the first generation. Representatives of the third generation include levofloxacin and moxifloxacin, which have further extended activity against Gram-positive bacteria.

Fluoroquinolones used to be among the most prescribed antibiotics, and resistance to them is now increasing. The administration of quinolone antibiotics carries a number of adverse effects (gastrointestinal symptoms, skin reactions, cartilage erosion, dizziness and confusion) (Baggio and Ananda-Rajah, 2021).

The mechanism of action of these antibiotics is inhibition of DNA synthesis and inhibition of the replication pathway. Quinolones inhibit two enzymes: topoisomerase IV and topoisomerase II (DNA gyrase), for Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, respectively (Aldred et al., 2014). DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV are essential enzymes in bacteria that manage the topological states of DNA during critical processes such as replication, transcription, and chromosome segregation (Tang and Zhao, 2023). These enzymes belong to the type II topoisomerase family and perform similar but distinct functions in maintaining DNA topology.

DNA gyrase introduces negative supercoils into DNA, which is crucial for compacting bacterial DNA and reducing torsional strain during replication and transcription (Shariati et al., 2022). It is the only topoisomerase that introduces negative supercoils using ATP hydrolysis. The enzyme is heterotetramer consists of two subunits: GyrA, responsible for DNA binding and strand breakage/rejoining, and GyrB, which provides ATPase activity for the supercoiling process. Topoisomerase IV primarily decatenates interlinked daughter chromosomes after replication, ensuring proper chromosome segregation (Shariati et al., 2022). It is also heterotetramer and consists of two subunits: ParC, with the same activity as GyrA, and ParE, which provides ATPase activity for decatenation.

The quinolone mode of action relies on the formation of a stable drug-enzyme-DNA complex. Quinolones bind to the DNA cleavage sites created by DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV, preventing the resealing of the DNA strands. A critical aspect of this binding involves the formation of a water-metal ion bridge, facilitated by a noncatalytic Mg²⁺, and a four water molecules. This bridge facilitating hydrogen bonding between the quinolone and key serine and acidic residues on the enzyme, which serve as anchor points for the drug (Correia et al., 2017).

Mechanisms of resistance to quinolones

Resistance to fluoroquinolones is not uncommon and is often associated with resistance to another antibiotic group. It can occur during antibiotic therapy, which is clinically significant (Pham et al., 2019). Resistance to fluoroquinolones in *S. aureus* can be caused by several mechanisms: chromosomal mutations, plasmid-acquired resistance genes, and efflux (which will be described in the chapter 3.8).

The most prevalent mechanism of resistance involves mutations in the quinolone-resistance determining regions (QRDRs) of the *gyrA* and *parC* genes, leading to amino acid substitutions (Huynh et al., 2023). These mutations can alter the structure of the enzyme's active site, disrupting the metal ion bridge formation and reducing the binding affinity of fluoroquinolones. Mutations in the *gyrB* and *parE* occur much less frequently compared to those in the *gyrA* and *parC*. Since serine and acidic residues that anchor the water-metal ion bridge are the most frequent amino acid substitutions linked to quinolone resistance, it is believed that disrupting this interaction between topoisomerases and quinolones leads to resistance (Correia et al., 2017). In both laboratory and clinical isolates, over 90 % of mutations involve serine substitutions, while changes at acidic residues account for most of the remaining mutations (Correia et al., 2017).

Another mechanism of resistance is plasmid-borne resistance, the danger of which lies primarily in its ability for not only vertical but also horizontal transmission. Plasmids also often carry resistance to multiple antibiotics. Here, resistance to quinolones is conferred by the *qnr* genes or the *aac(6)-Ib-cr* protein. The most frequently occurring Qnr protein in *S. aureus* is QnrA, which functions primarily as a protective factor for bacterial DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV (Hamza and Faza, 2023). It binds to these enzymes and shields them from the inhibitory effects of quinolones. The *aac(6)-Ib-cr* protein is an aminoglycoside acetyltransferase enzyme that, in addition to its role in aminoglycoside

resistance, also modifies quinolones. This protein acetylates quinolones, which impairs their ability to bind to their target enzymes, thereby reducing their antibacterial efficacy.

In general, staphylococci are well sensitive to fluoroquinolones and therefore changes in both enzymes are required to produce sufficient resistance - to increase MIC (Foster, 2017).

3.7.2. Sulfonamides and trimethoprim

Only two antibiotics from this class are used in human medicine. Sulfadiazine with silver as a topical antibiotic in treatment of burns and sulfamethoxazole in combination with trimethoprim (commercially in a 5:1 ratio) called cotrimoxazole used e.g., for treatment of urinary tract infections (Masters et al., 2003). It is an antibiotic that acts on Gram-negative bacteria and selected Gram-positive bacteria (including *S. aureus*). It is indicated for urinary tract infections, and possibly for skin and soft tissue infections caused by MRSA strains (Stevens et al., 2014), and is also used, for example, for the treatment and prophylaxis of pneumonia caused by *Pneumocystis jirovecii* (Haseeb et al., 2022). Its undeniable advantage is its relatively low resistance and affordability.

Sulfamethoxazole inhibits folic acid synthesis as a competitive antagonist of paraaminobenzoic acid (PABA) and is bacteriostatic. Trimethoprim is an inhibitor of bacterial dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR) and can act either bactericidal or bacteriostatic depending on the conditions (McCarter, 2017). Cotrimoxazole uses a combination of both antibiotics acting synergistically, allowing treatment of a wide range of bacterial infections. Folic acid, whose synthesis is affected by both compounds, is an absolutely essential cell growth factor (Foster, 2017).

Mechanism of resistance to sulfonamides and trimethoprim

Since neither sulfamethoxazole nor trimethoprim is used in monotherapy but in combination, mutations should theoretically be prevented (Goldberg and Bishara, 2012). In *S. aureus*, resistance to sulfonamides is caused by chromosomal mutations (in the gene encoding DHPS - dihydropteroate synthase) that lead to overproduction of PABA (1) and thus prevent the drug from binding to the enzyme (Foster, 2017). Resistance to trimethoprim is due to substitution of DHFR acid, (or its promoter) or is plasmid-encoded resistance (*dfr* genes in Enterobacteriaceae). Multiple resistance mechanisms may concurrently manifest within a single cell, increasing the level of resistance. Nevertheless, resistance to cotrimoxazole in *S. aureus* is still rare (occurrence in Asia) and is associated with the *dfrG* gene (Foster, 2017).

3.7.3. Rifamycins

Rifamycin was first isolated from the bacterium *Amycolatopsis rifamycinica* in 1959 (Sensi et al., 1960). Two years later, the semisynthetic 3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-iminomethyl derivative of rifamycin, rifampicin, was discovered. Rifampicin belongs to the class of ansamycin compounds. It is a polyketide characterized by a naphthoquinone core connected by an aliphatic ansa chain (Hardie and Fenn, 2022). Rifampicin (called rifampin in the USA), a broad-spectrum bactericidal antibiotic, is currently used. It is indicated primarily for the treatment of tuberculosis and Legionnaires' disease in long-term regimens. In these cases, it is important to monitor liver values because rifampicin is hepatotoxic and also has many drug interactions. At the time of administration, the patient should be advised of the possibility of discoloration of body fluids (urine, tears, and sweat) to red (Hardie and Fenn, 2022). It is also used to treat severe infections caused by *S. aureus* and MRSA due to its ability to penetrate biofilms and kill bacteria hiding in infected tissues. However, resistance can develop quickly if used as monotherapy, so it is usually paired with another antibiotic (e.g. fluoroquinolone) (Wang et al., 2019; Zheng et al., 2021). Rifampicin inhibits bacterial DNA-dependent RNA polymerase, crucial for transcription, by binding to a specific site on the enzyme (Zhang et al., 2023). It targets the DNA/RNA channel of the RNA polymerase β -subunit (RpoB). Rifampicin's ansa bridge and naphthol ring contain four hydroxyl groups that form hydrogen bonds with amino acids in the β -subunit (Hardie and

Fenn, 2022). This binding within the channel prevents the enzyme from elongating the RNA chain, effectively halting transcription. This action results in the inhibition of RNA synthesis, leading to cell death, particularly in rapidly dividing bacteria. Rifampicin is bactericidal, making it effective at killing bacteria rather than just inhibiting their growth.

Resistance to rifampicin in *S. aureus* typically arises through mutations in the *rpoB* gene, which result in amino acid sequence changes that alter the binding site, reducing rifampicin's affinity for RNA polymerase and leading to resistance (Zhang et al., 2023; Lee et al., 2022). These mutations are most common in the rifampicin resistance determining region (RRDR) of the *rpoB* gene and include, for example, L466S, H481N or H481Y (Wang et al., 2022b, 2019).

3.8. Efflux pumps

Bacterial efflux pumps are specialized transport systems distributed in the cytoplasmic membrane and serve as a natural defense mechanism. They actively pump various substances, including antibiotics, toxic compounds, virulence factors, dyes and detergents from the bacterial cell to the external environment. They may contribute to bacterial virulence by expelling toxic compounds originating from the host, allowing the pathogen to evade the host immune system and cause infection. In the case of biofilms, they may also contribute to the formation of chronic infections. Today, however, efflux pumps play a major role in the development of antibiotic resistance and multidrug resistance, primarily because they reduce the intracellular concentration of antimicrobial agents below therapeutic levels, thereby reducing their efficacy. The substrate specificity of efflux pumps, *i.e.* the ability of these pumps to remove specific substances from the bacterial cell, can be very diverse and depends on the type of efflux system. Each type of such system can be specialized to remove even single substance, but more often they are oriented towards structurally related substrates or, in the case of multidrug-resistant pumps, a wide range of structurally unrelated substances, which obviously contributes to their diversity and ability to survive in different environments. The expression of efflux pumps is often tightly regulated at the genetic level. Regulatory proteins control the activation or repression of efflux pump gene expression in response to environmental stimuli, including the presence of antibiotics. However, in strains with efflux-mediated resistance (such as HA-MRSA strains), the expression level of these strains is significantly elevated and often constitutive, resulting from mutations in promoter or regulatory genes (Dashtbani-Roozbehani and Brown, 2021). Bacteria can have both their own efflux pumps, which are part of their natural defense mechanisms, and acquired efflux pumps through horizontal gene transfer, leading to increased resistance.

Classification of efflux pumps

There are several families of efflux pumps, which are classified according to their structural conformation, their mechanism of action and other characteristics such as the homology of their sequences or the energy source used, of which the first five are the most clinically significant (Fig. 6):

1. ATB-binding cassette (ABC) superfamily
2. Major facilitator superfamily (MFS)
3. Multidrug and toxic compound extrusion (MATE) family
4. Small multidrug resistance (SMR) family
5. Resistance-nodulation division (RND) family
6. Proteobacterial antimicrobial compound efflux (PACE) family
7. *p*-aminobenzoyl-glutamate transporter (AbgT) family

The energy for efflux pump activity is obtained either from the hydrolysis of ATP, which is used by the ABC pump family and thus represents the primary transporters, or on the basis of the proton-motive force, *i.e.* from the antiport of the H⁺ ion per drug molecule, with the exception of the MATE family, where the Na⁺ ion can also participate in the exchange (Stevens et al., 2014). The other classes thus belong to the

Fig. 6. Clinically relevant bacterial efflux pumps. MATE – Multidrug and toxic compound extrusion family, MFS – Major facilitator superfamily, SMR – Small multidrug resistance family, ABC – ATP-binding cassette superfamily, RND – Resistance-nodulation division family.

secondary transporters.

Efflux pumps identified in the *S. aureus* genome mainly belong to the ABC, MFR, MATE and SMR families and more than 10 have been described to date. The FarE pump belonging to the RND family has been recently identified in *S. aureus* and serves to transport antimicrobial fatty acids found on skin and nasal secretions as an important component of human defense mechanisms (Dashtbani-Roozbehani and Brown, 2021; Alnaseri et al., 2015). Thus, FarE confers resistance to these fatty acids, such as linoleic and arachidonic acids (Alnaseri et al., 2015; Ding et al., 2023). RND pumps are typical of Gram-negative bacteria where they are tripartite and consist of an outer membrane protein (OMP), a membrane fusion protein (MFP) and an inner membrane protein (RND) (Nishino et al., 2021). However, FarE does not appear to have a classical tripartite structure due to the lack of an outer membrane in Gram-positive bacteria (Dashtbani-Roozbehani and Brown, 2021).

3.8.1. MFS efflux pumps of *S. aureus*

MFS is the most widespread family within all efflux pumps in bacteria, but also in humans. They are evolutionarily conserved across different bacterial species. The conservation of these transporters highlights their essential role in bacterial survival and adaptation to changing environments. MFS efflux pumps typically consist of 12 or 14 transmembrane helices (segments) that form a transport channel across the bacterial membrane. They exhibit a broad substrate specificity that allows efflux of different compounds and are therefore key contributors to bacterial multidrug resistance.

NorA is the first and, together with QacA, the most characterized efflux pump in *S. aureus*. Located on the chromosome, it consists of 12 helices and is known for its ability to efflux a wide range of substrates, including hydrophilic fluoroquinolone antibiotics such as ciprofloxacin and norfloxacin; tetracycline; chloramphenicol; quaternary ammonium compounds such as benzalkonium or cetrimide biocides; and dyes (e.g., ethidium bromide).

NorB and NorC are additional chromosomally encoded efflux pumps that confer resistance to both hydrophilic and hydrophobic fluoroquinolones, such as moxifloxacin, and to other disinfectants and dyes. NorB consists of 12 helices and NorC consists of 14 helices (Lekshmi et al., 2018). Today, Nor pumps are overexpressed in approximately 40 % of MRSA strains (Dashtbani-Roozbehani and Brown, 2021). Expression is regulated at the level of the multiple gene regulator (MgrA), which is encoded by *mgrA* gene. Thus, overexpression of these pumps in *mgrA* mutant strains confers complex fluoroquinolone resistance (Lekshmi et al., 2018).

The QacA and QacB pumps are plasmid-encoded and consist of 14 segments. They are known for their broad substrate specificity that allows them to actively pump a variety of cationic lipophilic compounds, including quaternary ammonium compounds (QACs), which are commonly used as disinfectants and antiseptics. Strains that acquire these genes on the plasmid are thus very dangerous, especially in the

hospital environment. Their expression is regulated by the *qacR* gene, which encodes the QacR transcription protein.

The MFS family of pumps also includes the specific tetracycline transporters TetK, TetL and Tet38. TetK can be located on both chromosome and plasmid, while TetL is carried only plasmid and Tet38 only chromosomally (Jensen and Lyon, 2009). TetK and TetL confer a high level of tetracycline resistance, while Tet38 has substrate specificity extended to some fatty acids (e.g., linoleic and palmitoleic), contributing to staphylococcal colonization of the skin, and phosphomycin (Lekshmi et al., 2018).

Other important staphylococcal MFS pumps include chromosomally encoded 14 segment transporters: SdrM conferring resistance to norfloxacin, biocides and some dyes, MdeA conferring resistance to fluoroquinolones (ciprofloxacin and norfloxacin) and macrolides, and LmrS conferring resistance to linezolid, lincomycin, chloramphenicol and, according to other sources, erythromycin, kanamycin, fusidic acid and trimethoprim (Lekshmi et al., 2018; Floyd et al., 2010; Vimberg et al., 2020b).

3.8.2. MATE efflux pumps of *S. aureus*

Within the MATE family, the only staphylococcal representative is the 12 segmented and chromosomally encoded MepA transporter associated with the MDR phenotype. It confers resistance to the fluoroquinolones ciprofloxacin, norfloxacin and moxifloxacin, as well as to glycylycylines such as tigecycline and various QAC group agents (Vimberg et al., 2020b).

3.8.3. SMR efflux pumps of *S. aureus*

As the name SMR family refers, its representatives are small efflux pumps consisting of four transmembrane helices forming homodimers in the cytoplasmic membrane. These include the plasmid-encoded QacC pump, often referred to as QacD or Smr, and the chromosomally encoded SepA pump. Both confer resistance to QACs and various dyes.

Understanding the role of efflux pumps in bacterial resistance is essential for developing strategies to combat multidrug-resistant bacteria and improve the efficacy of antibiotic therapy. Efflux pump inhibitors (EPIs) are compounds designed to block bacterial efflux pump activity. The combination of EPIs with antibiotics is now being investigated as a potential strategy to enhance the efficacy of commercially used antimicrobials.

4. Alternative therapies to combat antibiotic resistance in *Staphylococcus aureus*

As we have explored throughout this review, *S. aureus* employs a variety of sophisticated mechanisms to resist the effects of clinically relevant antibiotics. These strategies allow the bacterium to evade both the immune system and pharmacological interventions. The persistence of such resistance not only complicates treatment but also underscores

the urgent need for innovative approaches to combat this pathogen.

In light of the challenges posed by these resistance mechanisms, it is clear that relying solely on the development of new antibiotics may be insufficient. Future strategies must therefore encompass a broader spectrum of interventions, including the optimization of antibiotic use, the exploration of alternative therapies, and the advancement of diagnostic technologies. In the following section, we will discuss alternative and promising strategies that could help overcome antibiotic resistance, offering a multifaceted approach to secure more effective treatments for *Staphylococcus aureus* infections.

4.1. Search for new antimicrobial substances

To combat the growing resistance of *S. aureus*, the search for novel antimicrobial substances is essential. This section outlines several promising approaches.

4.1.1. Natural substances

The process of screening secondary metabolites from soil actinomycetes has traditionally led to the discovery of many antibiotics in use today. However, this method often has resulted in the rediscovery of known antibiotics or their close analogs, which has prompted researchers to seek new antibiotic sources from less conventional environments. These include marine ecosystems (such as invertebrates and algae), insects, and microbiomes. For example, four antibacterial compounds were purified from the extract of the marine fungi *Stachybotrys species* MF347, which showed *in vitro* activity against MRSA (Liu et al., 2019). Insect antimicrobial peptides such as thanatin also appear to be a potential weapon against resistance (Dash and Bhattacharjya, 2021).

Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are a diverse group of naturally occurring molecules that play a crucial role in the innate immune response of various organisms, including humans. They are recognized for their broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity against bacteria, fungi, viruses, and parasites and are therefore regaining attention as potential alternatives or adjuncts to conventional antibiotics. Several antimicrobial peptides are being investigated in clinical trials for the treatment of staphylococcal infections, such as LL-37 (Piller et al., 2022), OP-145 (Le et al., 2022), or brilacidin (Gajdacs, 2019).

4.1.2. New bacterial targets

Identifying new bacterial targets offers the potential to disrupt *S. aureus* in ways that current antibiotics do not, thereby circumventing existing resistance mechanisms. Some of the key targets include lipoteichoic acid synthesis (Gajdacs, 2019), filamenting temperature-sensitive Z protein (FtsZ) (Tripathy and Sahu, 2019), which is an attractive target for new antibiotics because of its essential role in cell division and its absence in human cells, or enoyl-acyl carrier protein reductase FabI, which is an essential enzyme involved in bacterial fatty acid biosynthesis (Bibens et al., 2023).

4.1.3. Small molecule libraries

High-throughput screening of small molecule libraries allows for the rapid identification of new antimicrobial candidates. A typical small-molecule library includes more than 10,000 synthetically produced chemical entities, each with diverse functional groups and structural frameworks. These small molecules can target novel bacterial processes or enhance the activity of existing antibiotics, offering a pathway to new drug development. For example, two potential substances HSGN-94 and HSGN-189 inhibiting lipoteichoic acid biosynthesis and showing activity against MRSA and VRE, were identified in this way (Bibens et al., 2023; Naclerio et al., 2019).

4.2. Alternative therapies

4.2.1. Adjuvant therapy

Adjuvant therapy involves the use of antibiotics in combination with

non-antibiotic agents, known as adjuvants, to enhance the effectiveness of the primary antimicrobial treatment. These adjuvants are specifically designed to inhibit mechanisms of resistance that bacteria employ to evade the effects of antibiotics. The most well-known combination therapy involves the use of beta-lactamase inhibitors, such as acid clavulanic, paired with beta-lactam antibiotics. Today, significant efforts are being directed towards identifying inhibitors for other critical bacterial resistance mechanisms beyond beta-lactamase enzymes. These include efflux pump inhibitors (EPI), Erm proteins inhibitors, aminoglycosid-modifying inhibitors (Dash and Bhattacharjya, 2021; Hurtová et al., 2024; Magaña et al., 2023). Many such inhibitors are plant-delivered and are from the group of alkaloids, flavonoids, or terpenoids (Magaña et al., 2023; Douglas et al., 2023).

4.2.2. Immunotherapy

Immunotherapy represents a powerful strategy in combating *Staphylococcus aureus* infections. By harnessing and enhancing the body's immune response, immunotherapy can provide an alternative or complementary approach to traditional antibiotic treatments.

Vaccines: Vaccines aim to prevent infections by stimulating the immune system to recognize and respond to *Staphylococcus aureus* before it can cause disease. Despite the challenges in developing a vaccine against this versatile pathogen, there have been significant advances in this area (Chand et al., 2023). Although no *S. aureus* vaccine has yet been approved for clinical use, ongoing research continues to explore various antigen combinations and delivery systems to enhance vaccine efficacy and provide long-term protection.

Immunoconjugates: Specifically antibiotic-antibody conjugates (AACs) are innovative therapeutic agents that combine the specificity of antibodies with the bactericidal power of antibiotics. This approach enhances the precision and efficacy of antibiotic therapy. The antibody component of the conjugate is designed to specifically bind to *S. aureus* surface antigens, such as surface proteins or polysaccharides. Once bound, the attached antibiotic is delivered directly to the bacterial cell, maximizing its local concentration and effectiveness. This targeted delivery minimizes collateral damage to the host's healthy microbiota and reduces the risk of systemic side effects. Additionally, the focused action of the antibiotic helps limit the development of resistance. One such AAC is DSTA4637S, which is composed of a monoclonal human IgG antibody engineered to specifically bind to teichoic acid β -O-linked N-acetylglucosamine sugars on the *S. aureus* surface. This antibody is modified to include unpaired cysteine residues, allowing for the attachment of a rifamycin derivative via a cathepsin-cleavable linker (Douglas et al., 2023). DSTA4637S has demonstrated the ability to efficiently opsonize MRSA circulating in the bloodstream, facilitating their uptake by phagocytic immune cells. Once inside these cells, intracellular proteases cleave the linker, releasing the active antibiotic in high concentrations to effectively kill intracellular *S. aureus* (Douglas et al., 2023; Peck et al., 2019).

4.2.3. Phage and phage lysine therapy

Phage therapy involves the use of bacteriophages viruses that specifically target and lyse bacterial cells. This method leverages the natural specificity of phages, which can selectively infect and destroy *S. aureus* without affecting human cells or beneficial bacteria (Atshan et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2024a). Phages work by attaching to bacterial surfaces, injecting their genetic material, and hijacking the bacterial machinery to replicate and produce new phages, which eventually lead to the lysis and death of the bacterial cell (Liu et al., 2024a). The evolving nature of phages allows them to adapt to bacterial resistance mechanisms, offering a potentially enduring solution to resistant infections.

Phage lysins are enzymes produced by bacteriophages that break down bacterial cell walls, causing cell lysis. These lysins target specific components of the bacterial cell wall, leading to rapid bacterial death. Their precise action makes them effective against a broad range of strains within a bacterial species, and they are less likely to induce

resistance compared to traditional antibiotics. Phage lysins hold promise for both topical and systemic applications, providing a rapid and targeted approach to infection control.

4.2.4. Probiotic therapy

Staphylococcal infections like staphylococcal food poisoning, bacteremia or endocarditis are typically acute, which may explain the limited research on their interaction with gastrointestinal microbiota. However, studies indicate that *S. aureus* can adhere to intestinal mucus and disrupt gut microbial balance in both humans and animal models. This disruption, or dysbiosis, can impair the intestinal immune system, potentially affecting overall immunity and leading to bacterial translocation to other parts of the body. As a result, maintaining gut microbial balance through methods like prebiotics, bacterial peptides, or fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT) may be a promising therapeutic approach to reduce susceptibility to *S. aureus* infections (Liu et al., 2024b).

4.2.5. CRISPR-Cas therapy

CRISPR-Cas therapy is an advanced gene-editing technique that targets antibiotic-resistant bacteria, including *S. aureus*. The CRISPR-Cas system, which can be programmed to recognize and cut specific DNA sequences, may effectively disrupt genes associated with antibiotic resistance or virulence. By targeting and eliminating resistance genes, CRISPR-Cas can reduce the bacteria's ability to resist treatment and potentially reverse resistance, making bacteria susceptible to existing antibiotics. It can also directly induce bacterial cell death by creating double-stranded breaks in essential genes.

The therapy promises precision in targeting resistant strains without harming beneficial microbiota and could help to extend the efficacy of current antibiotics. However, challenges such as effective delivery, minimizing off-target effects, and managing immune responses need to be addressed. As research progresses, CRISPR-Cas therapy could become a vital tool in combating antibiotic-resistant infections.

5. Novel drug delivery system

Advanced drug delivery systems (DDS) are often superior to traditional antibiotics due to their ability to deliver drugs directly to the site of infection, enhancing drug concentration where it is needed most. DDS also allows for controlled and sustained release of antibiotics, reducing the need for high doses and frequent administration, which lowers the risk of toxicity and side effects. Additionally, DDS can protect antibiotics from degradation, ensuring they remain potent upon reaching the infection site. This targeted approach may also reduce the development of resistance by limiting the exposure of bacteria to suboptimal drug levels, a common issue with traditional antibiotic treatments.

Commonly developed types of these systems include polymeric nanoparticles, organic or metal-based nanoparticles, liposomes and others. Polymeric nanoparticles are made from biodegradable polymers like polylactic acid, polyglycolic acid or polyethylene glycol. For the treatment of staphylococcal infections were developed, for example: hyaluronic acid polymerosomes entrapping vancomycin (Walvekar et al., 2019), or ciprofloxacin-loaded polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) hydrogels (Thamilselvan et al., 2023). Within metal-based nanoparticles, for example, silver nanoparticles are being developed to inhibit staphylococcal toxins and enzymes (Joshi and Patil, 2023). Liposomes for dual-drug (vancomycin, daptomycin) delivery against MRSA were also published (Rani et al., 2022).

As researchers explore and develop alternative strategies to overcome antibiotic resistance in *Staphylococcus aureus*, it is crucial to remember that effective treatment is not solely dependent on the antibiotic or therapeutic intervention. The success of any antimicrobial approach also hinges on its interaction with the human immune system, which is a crucial factor that can influence the efficacy of antimicrobial therapy. While antibiotics are primarily designed to target bacterial

pathogens, their effects extend beyond just eliminating microorganisms. Increasing evidence suggests that antibiotics can modulate the host immune response, which in turn can significantly impact therapeutic outcomes through various mechanisms, including direct effects on immune cells, alteration of the host microbiota, and modulation of inflammatory pathways.

5.1. Direct effects on immune cells

Several antibiotics have been shown to interact with immune cells, leading to immunomodulatory effects. Macrolides such as azithromycin and clarithromycin, for example, possess immunostimulatory properties. They can inhibit the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines like IL-6 and TNF- α , thereby reducing excessive inflammatory responses that could otherwise damage tissues (Manaia et al., 2024). Beta-lactam antibiotics, including penicillins and cephalosporins, have been reported to influence the activity of neutrophils and macrophages, potentially enhancing phagocytosis and aiding in the clearance of bacterial pathogens (Mondemé et al., 2023). However, boosting the activity of immune cells could also lead to excessive inflammation. For example, in severe cases of *S. aureus* sepsis, an overactive immune response could contribute to the development of systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) or multiple organ failure (Huang et al., 2019).

5.2. Alteration of the host microbiota

The human microbiota, particularly the gut microbiota, plays a critical role in regulating the immune system. Antibiotics, especially broad-spectrum agents, can disrupt the balance of the microbiota, leading to dysbiosis (Fishbein et al., 2023). This disruption can impair gut health and immune function, increasing susceptibility to secondary infections, such as *Clostridium difficile* overgrowth (Fishbein et al., 2023; Patangia et al., 2022). Altered microbiota can also modify immune responses and drug metabolism, potentially reducing antibiotic effectiveness and increasing the risk of adverse effects. Therefore, managing the impact of antibiotics on intestinal microflora is crucial for maintaining therapeutic efficacy and overall health.

5.3. Modulation of inflammatory pathways

Antibiotics can also influence the inflammatory environment within the host. For example, tetracyclines are known to inhibit matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) and downregulate the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, leading to reduced tissue damage in inflammatory diseases (Tosi et al., 2024). However, in the context of bacterial infections, this anti-inflammatory effect could potentially impair the host's ability to mount an effective immune response, thereby impacting the overall efficacy of antibiotic treatment.

Understanding how these alternative therapies can work in synergy with the body's natural defenses is essential for creating comprehensive and sustainable treatment strategies. Therefore, alongside the innovation of new therapeutic agents, attention must be given to how these interventions enhance or complement immune responses, maximizing their efficacy in combating resistant infections.

6. Conclusion

As shown above bacteria exhibit remarkable adaptability and innovation in their strategies to survive in environments abundant with hazardous compounds. The rapid proliferation of a large bacterial population in the selective environment of antibiotics provides an ideal setting for the emergence of resistant mutants. Therefore, it is not surprising that bacteria have evolved highly efficient and redundant mechanisms of resistance to all currently employed antibiotics. The need for a fast response and the exploration of novel approaches to mitigate infections caused by antibiotic-resistant bacteria has become

imperative. These may include use of bacteriophages or adjuvant therapy or employing adjuvant therapies intended to restore the susceptibility of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains to antibiotics.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tomáš Ruml: Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision. **Jitka Viktorová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Daniela Brdová:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests Jitka Viktorova reports financial support was provided by The project National Institute of virology and bacteriology (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5103) - Funded by the European Union - Next Generation EU. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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